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**Adaptive Bayesian Inference Under Bounded Constraints: Agent-
Based Modelling of Utility and Stability in Dynamic
Environments**

by

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Abstract

Why do cognitive systems maintain beliefs that are not strictly accurate yet remain adaptive? This dissertation addresses this question by reframing Bayesian inference in teleonomic terms: inference is treated not as accuracy maximisation but as the regulation of fitness utility and representational stability under ecological constraints. The central research question was how agents with increasingly utility- and context-sensitive priors, and coherence-sensitive adaptation, perform relative to a flat-prior baseline across payoff, relative advantage, coherence, and adaptability under volatility. An agent-based simulation was implemented in MATLAB using a two-alternative forced-choice (threat vs. non-threat) categorisation task with asymmetric payoffs and hazard-driven regime shifts. Four agents were specified: (A) a flat-prior Bayesian observer, (B) a schema-biased observer, (C) an affect-modulated observer, and (D) using a utility- and coherence-preserving update dynamics that balanced stability with adaptability, keeping beliefs steady when evidence was uncertain but adjusting more strongly when mismatches persisted. Agents were evaluated across four dimensions: epistemic fit, instrumental utility, coherence stability, and adaptive efficiency. Hypotheses targeted cumulative payoff (H1), relative advantage (H2), and coherence stability (H3a–b), the latter indexed by a Coherence Stability Index (CSI) and counts of Kullback–Leibler divergence spikes. Prespecified contrasts were tested using Bayesian paired t-tests. Results supported all hypotheses. Enriched agents (B–D) achieved higher payoffs than the baseline ($D > C > A > B$). Agent D showed the lowest relative advantage, the highest CSI in volatile blocks, and fewer coherence disruptions than Agents A and B, with a modest margin over Agent C. These findings suggest that adaptive performance under uncertainty depends on both ecological calibration and coherence-preserving update control. While limited by its stylised design, the study provides a tractable platform for modelling utility- and coherence-sensitive inference in complex environments.

Human cognition continues to pose challenging questions for both philosophy and psychology. Among these is a central inquiry: why do mental representations not only have the content they do, but also exhibit characteristic tendencies – persistence, resistance to change, and, at times, systematic distortion? Teleosemantic accounts address the first part of this puzzle by linking representational content to function: mental states take the shape they do because the mechanisms that produce and use them were selected for in evolutionary history or through learning-like selection where behaviours or states are differentially retained through reinforcement over a lifetime, in order to guide adaptive behaviour (Millikan, 1989; Neander, 2017). This teleological reading, on its own, does not resolve empirical questions about cognitive dynamics, but it does help explain why certain tendencies may be adaptive. For example, pain that is difficult to ignore (stability), vigilance biases that over-detect threats (distortion), or identity-protective, emotionally motivated beliefs that resist disconfirmation (rigidity) may each have historically supported viability. The use of this perspective here is explanatory and methodological rather than doctrinal: teleosemantics provides a naturalistic basis for notions of correctness and misrepresentation (Kiefer & Hohwy, 2017), while longstanding debates and objections lie outside the scope of the present simulation.

This functional framing aligns with mechanistic accounts in contemporary cognitive science, where Bayesian approaches formalise internal models as the integration of priors (expectations from past experience) with sensory evidence. Prediction errors signal mismatches between expectation and input; when weighted by precision (their estimated reliability within the model), they drive belief revision (Rescorla, 2021). Predictive Processing (PP) extends this framework into a hierarchical architecture, in which higher levels generate predictions and lower levels return precision-weighted errors (Clark, 2013).

Within this inferential view, the present focus shifts to the dynamics of belief change under ecological constraint. A central challenge for cognition is how to remain flexible enough to revise in light of error, while stable enough to preserve an organised orientation to the world (Rescorla, 2021; Shea, 2023). Francisco Varela's (1991) notion of internal coherence captures this orientation within biology: the preservation of an autonomous system's organisational closure and structural coupling, allowing it to remain viable amid perturbation (Gallagher & Zahavi, 2020). Coherence does not imply stasis. Beliefs and perceptions adjust continually in response to error signals, but these adjustments are integrated into a broader stability that sustains adaptive functioning. In this sense, coherence highlights a deeper tension within cognitive systems – between the need to adapt to changing input and the need to preserve a functional organisation that resists collapse (Friston, 2010; Shea, 2023).

These considerations hint towards the potential value of a more explicit teleonomic perspective within Bayesian inference, by which internal states are constructed with the objective of maximising fitness utility (Geisler, 2010), and subsequent representational dynamics are evaluated not by their veridicality alone, but by their role in sustaining viability under various constraints (Gallagher & Zahavi, 2020). From this view, persistence, resistance to change, and systematic distortion can be better understood as adaptive products of evolutionary history – mechanisms that favour viability and representational stability within an internal model of the world when the costs of error are asymmetric or when shaped by the limits of cognitive and ecological constraints (Haselton et al., 2009). By coupling Varela's (1991) internal coherence with a teleonomic reading of Bayesian inference, we may begin to better explain why certain beliefs often endure or skew in predictable ways: not merely as cognitive shortcuts or flaws, but as functionally tuned strategies for maintaining adaptive and organised engagement in volatile and uncertain environments (Carr, 2017; Kiefer & Hohwy,

2017).

1.2 Problem Statement and Research Gap

Probabilistic models, such as Predictive Processing (PP), offer a powerful computational-mechanistic account of how mental representations are formed and updated within internal and external statistical structures. Here, cognition is characterised as hierarchical inferential computation instantiated in neural circuits, elegantly explaining processes such as perception, perceptual illusions, and adaptive estimation (Clark, 2013; Friston, 2010). However, these models are typically cast in terms of accuracy first, with survival and agency treated as downstream consequences. As a result, they provide less traction on why internal representations have the specific contents they do, or why they exhibit characteristic tendencies such as persistence, resistance to change, or systematic distortion. Such deviations from accuracy are often interpreted as biases, heuristics, or belief rigidity – in other words, as computational shortcomings relative to a rational Bayesian ideal, undermining their functional role (Wiese, 2016).

From an evolutionary perspective, such distortions can be reinterpreted as utility-weighted trade-offs. Categorisation, for example, reduces computational load and supports memory but necessarily sacrifices within-category discrimination and global fidelity. As Hammerstein (2012) asserts, even a perfectly rational observer would still need to model evolved human psychology to act optimally; separating normative ideals from descriptive mechanisms is untenable in practice. This motivates a shift away from accuracy-first formulations toward a teleonomic, utility-sensitive account of inference – one that embeds probabilistic mechanisms within a broader evolutionary and functional framework and

explicitly incorporates motivational and adaptive dimensions (Haselton et al., 2009; Rescorla, 2024).

A related concern arises from Savage's distinction between "small worlds" and "large worlds" (Binmore, 2007). Rational actor models perform well in bounded small worlds where hypotheses are specified, distributions are stationary, and payoffs are transparent. But as Brighton and Gigerenzer (2012) note, in large-world conditions of volatility, misspecification, and limited observability, axiomatic rationality collapses. Human cognition evolved for precisely these large-world settings, where rationality must be viability-oriented rather than purely axiomatic (Gigerenzer & Gaissmaier, 2011). From this perspective, what matters is not strict conformity to economic or logical norms but whether inference supports survival and reproduction (Houston, 2012). Bayesian inference should therefore be read biologically – as fitness-sensitive rather than epistemically pristine (Haselton et al., 2009). This reframing clarifies what humans actually maximise: not accuracy for its own sake, but outcomes shaped by evolved preference architectures. Desires themselves are structured by inclusive-fitness pressures (West et al., 2012), and priors are biased toward outcomes that historically enhanced viability (Gigerenzer, 2002; Johnson & Fowler, 2011). On this account, systematic "distortions" – from perceptual illusions to vigilance biases or identity-protective beliefs – are not departures from rationality but instances of fitness utility-weighted Bayesian cognition (Gigerenzer, 2008).

Motivational accounts of belief dynamics reinforce this survival-focused view. Identity protection explains why beliefs tied to self-concept or group affiliation are particularly resistant to change. Motivated reasoning highlights how affective states bias information processing toward emotionally stabilising conclusions (Gesiarz et al., 2019; Kahan, 2016). Threat-management accounts demonstrate how clinging to simple or rigid

beliefs can reduce anxiety and restore control in uncertain situations (Branscombe & Wann, 1994). Each reflects not arbitrary error but adaptive mechanisms that preserve coherence under pressure, even at the cost of accuracy (Gigerenzer & Gaissmaier, 2011). Such processes may extend beyond low-level perception into abstract, affective, and identity-relevant beliefs (Lo & Zhang, 2021; Rigoli et al., 2021). In ancestral contexts, salient threats were typically physical, such as predators. In contemporary contexts, however, many of the most consequential threats are symbolic – relating to identity, belonging, or values – but they elicit affective and physiological responses akin to those evolved for physical danger (Branscombe & Wann, 1994; Slavich, 2020). This reflects an evolutionary mismatch, whereby mechanisms calibrated for immediate survival in ancestral environments are redeployed in symbolic and social domains, helping to explain the rigidity of identity-protective beliefs in the face of counterevidence (Haselton et al., 2009).

Despite recognition of bounded rationality and ecological utility, there is limited formal modelling of how such evolved priors operate across multiple functional levels – from sensory predictions to higher-order conceptual and affective states – and how they may interact as mechanisms for conservative belief updating under environmental uncertainty (Lo & Zhang, 2021). Constructs such as belief rigidity, dissonance reduction, and resistance to updating highlight the adaptive need for stability; yet these remain fragmented across the literatures (Vanpaemel & Navarro, 2007). Recasting them within a teleonomic perspective highlights internal coherence as a potentially adaptive function: the organised maintenance of belief systems that resist disruptive error while permitting strategic reorganisation when pressures become overwhelming (Bombardi, 2013; Gigerenzer, 2002).

The relevance of this project lies in formally testing how stability, bias, and representational adaptability trade off under volatility. By simulating agents with distinct

prior structures and adaptive logics, it seeks to clarify when fidelity to input is maintained, when systematic distortions enhance performance, and how stability can be preserved without stasis. Essentially, if strategy choice is outsourced to selection and learning, then priors and precisions should be read as empirical, fitness-tuned constraints rather than unexplained explainers (Rescorla, 2024). This project contributes a principled vocabulary and reproducible modelling framework for understanding why evolved priors sometimes lead to favouring internal stability over truth, and how such biases may constitute rational strategies under bounded and ecological constraints in volatile and complex environments (Gigerenzer, 2002).

1.3 Principles, Aim, and Objectives

Building on the considerations identified above, this dissertation operationalises three guiding principles intended to advance computational models of inference that incorporate utility sensitivity (Geisler, 2003), complementing evolutionary perspectives on the content and dynamics of mental representation (Wiese, 2016; Vanpaemel & Navarro, 2007).

First, because priors are shaped by evolutionary, developmental, and affective constraints, a taxonomy of priors is required to capture how expectations influence inference across distinct functional levels (Barrett, 2016; Geisler, 2003; Maloney & Mamassian, 2009; Martignon et al., 2003). In the simulation, this principle is expressed through agents that differ in their prior structures, ranging from accuracy-oriented baselines to schematic-based and affect-biased variants.

Furthermore, because accuracy-first models provide little traction on adaptive distortions, a teleonomic stance on Bayesian modelling is adopted. This frames cognition as fitness-oriented rather than accuracy-maximising, emphasising outcomes that maximise

fitness utility and preserve viability over strictly veridical representations (Geisler, 2003; Rescorla, 2024). It is instantiated in agents whose updating rules balanced statistical fit with utility- and coherence-sensitive adjustments.

Finally, because persistence and rigidity can sometimes support adaptive coherence, prior work highlights how belief systems balance stability with flexibility (Vanpaemel & Navarro, 2007). Drawing on Varela's (1991) account of autonomous systems, coherence-preserving processes may modulate beliefs – resisting change while still reorganising in response to significant prediction errors (Gallagher & Zahavi, 2020; Friston, 2010). This perspective provides the conceptual rationale for the adaptive agent's modulation of learning rates and decision weights to maintain functional stability under volatility.

The aim of this dissertation is thus to investigate how different Bayesian agents adapt under ecological constraints, focusing on the trade-off between representational fidelity, adaptive bias, and belief stability. Rather than seeking wholesale validation of a single comprehensive scheme, the study implements the three principles above through theory-informed structures for priors, learning rules, and adaptive modulation as a means to investigate their plausibility. Specifically, the objectives are: (i) to implement an agent-based simulation of a two-alternative forced-choice (2AFC) threat–non-threat task with asymmetric utilities and hazard-driven regime switches; (ii) to compare four agent classes that differ in their prior structures updating rules, and adaptation logics; (iii) to assess performance using both accuracy metrics and measures emphasising utility and stability; and (iv) to evaluate how evolved priors and adaptive updating influence performance across stable and volatile environments.

1.4 Research Question, Hypotheses, and Methodological Overview

The central research question guiding this dissertation is: How do agents with increasingly utility- and context-sensitive priors, and adaptive updating mechanisms, compare to a flat-prior baseline across fitness payoff, relative advantage, coherence stability, and adaptability under hazard-driven regime shifts? To address this, a tractable agent-based simulation was developed using a two-alternative forced-choice (2AFC) threat–non-threat categorisation task with asymmetric utilities and hazard-driven regime switches. Four agent classes were implemented with increasingly complex inference mechanisms: a flat-prior, accuracy-oriented baseline (Agent A); a schema-biased conceptual prior (Agent B); an affective-modulated prior variant (Agent C); and an adaptive agent (Agent D) integrating utility weighting and entropy costs with coherence-preserving learning-rate mechanisms.

Performance was evaluated using both standard accuracy metrics (e.g., ROC AUC) and measures foregrounding utility and stability. These included cumulative fitness payoff, relative advantage (posterior-Bayes oracle payoff minus realised payoff; lower is better and values can be negative), coherence stability (measured with a Coherence Stability Index, CSI, combining a moving-window posterior variance term with an exponentially smoothed accuracy trace; higher CSI values indicate greater representational stability under volatility), and post-shift disruption counts (measured as spikes in Kullback–Leibler divergence between successive posteriors, marking abrupt coherence disruptions). Four hypotheses were thus tested at the level of agent-class contrasts and task regimes, with inferential analyses conducted using Bayesian paired t-tests under a default Cauchy prior (Lee & Wagenmakers, 2014). It was hypothesised, first, that hierarchical agents (B–D) would achieve higher cumulative fitness payoffs than baseline Agent A, with the largest advantage anticipated for Agent D, in line with models of utility-based inference (Rescorla, 2024). Second, Agent D

was expected to minimise relative advantage relative to Agents A-C, reflecting the expectation that stability-preserving mechanisms may improve their efficiency of converting information into those favouring utility maximising outcomes (Lee & Wagenmakers, 2014; Rescorla, 2024). Third, in volatile blocks, Agent D was expected to exhibit higher CSI (i.e., greater representational stability) compared to Agents A-C, consistent with predictive processing accounts that emphasise suppressing unnecessary fluctuations in belief states under unstable and complex conditions (Clark, 2016). Finally, following regime shifts, Agent D was predicted to produce fewer KL divergence spikes than Agents A–C, indicating superior buffering against coherence disruptions during belief updating (Friston, 2010). Robustness was ensured through multiple random-seed runs ($n = 50$) and parameter sensitivity analyses (Appendix C). Full operational definitions and mathematical formulations of all measures are provided in Section 3 and Appendix B to ensure transparency and reproducibility. The research complied with BPS Ethical Standards and Guidelines.

2. Theoretical Background

2.1 Philosophical Foundations of Constructed Cognition

Philosophical debates have long held that cognition does not simply mirror reality but actively structures it. Kant famously argued that perception is shaped by a priori categories – pre-existing frameworks such as space, time, and causality – so that we experience only phenomena as filtered through these structures, not reality in itself (Guyer, 2007). Later thinkers, such as Schopenhauer, added that perception is imbued with affect and motivation (Wicks, 2017), laying the foundation for a constructivist approach in which cognition is understood as an interpretive process shaped by internal structures, affective states and ecological context (Ültanır, 2012; Noë, 2004). The present analysis grounds the treatment of priors as adaptive constructs whose utility-maximising and practical adequacy can be

empirically tested through simulation, providing an operational contrast to the philosophical debate between truth and survival.

2.2 Constructed Cognition: Mental Representation, Coherence and Constructivist-Pragmatism

Constructivist and pragmatist perspectives take the view that mental representations are not passive mirrors of reality but tools whose adequacy lies in sustaining viable engagement with the world (Piaget, 1967; Peirce, 1878; James, 1907; Legg & Hookway, 2008; Williams, 2017). Here, beliefs are judged less by strict correspondence than by their ability to “work,” enabling assimilation, accommodation, and successful action. Coherentist theories extend this emphasis by treating justification as a property of whole networks rather than isolated beliefs, where stability depends on mutual support, explanatory integration, and the minimisation of anomalies (Quine, 1963; Murphy, 2006; Bombardi, 2013; Young, 2018). Varela’s (1991) account of biological self-organisation offers a naturalistic analogue: coherence arises from the interplay of neural, bodily, and environmental processes that together sustain a system’s identity under perturbation (Gallagher & Zahavi, 2020). Across these perspectives, coherence is framed not as a fixed state but as a dynamic constraint in which representations remain viable when sufficiently integrated to preserve stability while still adapting to disruption. This conceptualisation provides a backdrop for treating coherence as a property worth examining alongside utility and accuracy in contemporary cognitive frameworks (Williams, 2018).

2.3 The Shift from Representationalism in Contemporary Cognitive Science

Contemporary cognitive science increasingly frames representation in pragmatic rather than strictly veridical terms that align with reality. The Bayesian brain hypothesis treats

the mind as if it were an “ideal observer,” integrating priors with sensory evidence to generate posterior beliefs under uncertainty (Knill & Pouget, 2004; Friston, 2010). This stance has unified accounts across perception, motor control, and learning (Rescorla, 2024); however, it is best understood as a computational-level benchmark rather than a literal process theory. This is because exact Bayesian inference is biologically implausible and human performance shows systematic departures from optimality (Tenenbaum et al., 2011; Rescorla, 2024). Predictive Processing (PP) extends this logic, casting the brain as a hierarchical prediction engine where mismatches (prediction errors) drive updating, and precision weighting regulates the influence of priors versus incoming evidence (Clark, 2013). In this framing, the value of representation lies not in mirroring the world but in sustaining adaptive regulation and guiding action under uncertainty. The Free Energy Principle (FEP) generalises this orientation, presenting a normative principle that organisms must minimise free energy – an upper bound on surprise – to maintain viable states within their ecological niches (Friston, 2010; Ramstead et al., 2016). Taken together, these frameworks mark a shift from correspondence-based accuracy toward viability under constraint: reducing costly errors, regulating uncertainty, and enabling coherent engagement with the environment (Rescher, 2012; Bombardi, 2013; Clark, 2013).

Figure 1

Schematic overview of the Teleonomic Bayesian Inference (TBI) framework and its simulation realisation. The diagram shows the relationship between stimuli, agents' priors and updates, decision processes and key evaluation metrics.

2.4 Teleonomic Bayesian Inference (TBI): a Modelling Stance

Teleonomic Bayesian Inference (TBI) is a modelling stance that treats inference as utility-sensitive and resource-bounded: belief states are evaluated not by accuracy alone, but by their capacity to secure fitness while conserving representational resources. From this perspective, systematic distortions – such as vigilance biases or coherence-preserving conservatism – can be adaptive when they reduce costly errors under ecological constraints (Geisler, 2010; Trimmer et al., 2011; Williams, 2021).

Formally, the stance can be expressed as:

$$b^* = \operatorname{argmax}_{b \in \mathcal{B}} [Ee \sim P(E|b)U(e, b) - C_{\text{resources}}(b)],$$

where $U(e, b)$ denotes expected fitness utility, and

$$C_{\text{resources}}(b) = F_U(b) + \delta H(q_b)$$

combines a computational cost term with an entropy penalty. This expression serves as a conceptual objective function, highlighting the trade-off between utility gains and representational costs. It was not solved directly in the simulations but provided the guiding principle for how agents were designed and assessed.

Figure 1 (schematic) illustrates this stance. At the top, the TBI objective highlights the balance between fitness utility and representational costs. In the middle, stimuli feed into priors (Agents A-D), likelihoods, and posteriors that generate decisions and payoffs. At the bottom, evaluation metrics such as payoff, relative advantage, and coherence stability (CSI) operationalise the stance and provide a theory informed measure.

In practice, Agent D embodied this TBI principle through an update process that favoured stability when evidence was uncertain, but allowed stronger adjustments when mismatches persisted. This produced conservative belief revisions under ambiguity, while enabling flexibility once discrepancies became significant. Importantly, decision criteria themselves remained fixed, adaptation occurred through the strength of updates rather than by shifting thresholds. TBI may therefore provide a potentially useful framework: accuracy and parsimony remain important, but they are subordinated to the broader teleonomic aim of sustaining viability under bounded conditions. The following sections detail how this stance informed the simulation environment, with formal definitions and parameters presented in Methods and Appendix B.

2.5 Evolutionary Foundations and Multi-Level Constraints

Cognition is the product of evolutionary pressures that tuned the brain to systemic and ecological demands (Bender, 2019). Rather than providing transparent access to reality, these pressures constrained the space of viable mental representations, shaping how they arise, stabilise, and adapt under changing conditions (Godfrey-Smith, 1996). With limited metabolic resources and bandwidth, natural selection favoured efficiency and behavioural relevance over objective fidelity, such that perception functions as a compressed, action-oriented code rather than a veridical map (Hoffman et al., 2015; Prakash et al., 2021).

Campbell's (1974) evolutionary epistemology captures this logic: cognitive mechanisms evolve through Darwinian selection for adaptive fit, with reliability grounded in survival utility rather than transparent truth-tracking. He distinguished between the evolution of epistemic mechanisms (EEM) – perceptual and cognitive capacities shaped by natural selection – and the evolution of epistemic theories (EET), where trial-and-error learning

refines systems of knowledge. On a phylogenetic scale, traits stabilise across generations as evolutionarily stable strategies where representational and behavioural dispositions are conserved not for their truth-tracking accuracy, but for the adaptive resilience they afford under volatile ancestral conditions (Hammerstein, 2012). On the ontogenetic scale, development reorganises inherited structures across the lifespan. Genetic potentials constrain but do not fully determine outcomes, leaving room for ecological interactions to shape how cognitive architectures are tuned. This process influences how representations are formed, stabilised, and adapted over time (Gottlieb, 1991).

This developmental tuning occurs against the backdrop of ecological pressures, where organisms must also navigate trade-offs across multiple currencies such as energy versus predation risk, or mean returns versus variance in outcomes (Houston, 2012). Under such conditions, cognition rarely achieves global optimisation; instead, it succeeds through satisficing (pursuing a course of action that will satisfy the minimum requirements necessary to achieve a particular goal) heuristics that balance precision against resilience under constraint (Gigerenzer, 2002; Haselton et al., 2009). These constraints operate at nested levels. Biological limits restrict what can be sensed or computed, developmental processes tune inherited architectures across the lifespan through ecological and social input, and cultural scaffolds add further constraints through language, norms, and symbolic systems (Bronfenbrenner, 1979; Heyes, 2018; Tomasello, 2014). The cumulative effect is that representational content and dynamics are not neutral depictions of reality but cost-efficient constructions shaped to maximise survival utility under constraint (Garland et al., 2021; Heras-Escribano, 2020). Building on this foundation, the present project operationalises these influences within Bayesian generative models, enabling their impact on representational content and dynamics to be examined under ecologically relevant conditions.

2.6 Adaptive Interfaces: Perception and Cognition under Constraint

If cognition arises under evolutionary and systemic limits, it is best understood as an adaptive interface tuned for survival utility rather than a veridical reconstruction of reality. Beliefs and representations retain relative correspondence to the world, but only as compressed, action-oriented codes that prioritise behavioural relevance over exhaustive accuracy (Rescorla, 2024; Campbell, 1974). Gibson's (1979) notion of affordances and Uexküll's (1957) concept of the Umwelt both illustrate this ecological stance: organisms perceive opportunities for action within a species-specific perceptual world that encodes survival-relevant cues. Hoffman and colleagues formalise this insight in the Interface Theory of Perception, showing through evolutionary game-theoretic models that agents tuned to fitness payoffs consistently outcompete veridical perceivers, suggesting that perception operates as a simplified interface optimised for viability (Hoffman et al., 2015; Prakash et al., 2021).

This framing extends to cognition. Simon's (1956) principle of bounded rationality emphasises that decision-making is constrained by time, memory, and metabolic resources, such that satisficing (good-enough solutions) takes precedence over global optimisation. Gigerenzer's work on ecological rationality shows that heuristics succeed when they are tuned to environmental structure, balancing tractability against error (Gigerenzer & Todd, 1999; Brighton & Gigerenzer, 2012). Cognitive systems often compress continua into categories to reduce complexity, a process that aids efficiency but introduces systematic biases (Wolff, 2019). From a teleonomic perspective, such biases can be adaptive when they reduce costly errors under uncertainty (Haselton et al., 2009; Trimmer et al., 2011). Error Management Theory (EMT) captures this asymmetry, showing that when the costs of false negatives outweigh those of false positives, natural selection favours precautionary

biases even at the expense of accuracy (Haselton & Buss, 2000). Nesse's (2001) smoke detector principle generalises this logic: false alarms are adaptive when misses can be catastrophic. These principles also help explain optimism biases and desirability effects, where evidence is weighted toward favourable outcomes, reflecting an evolved tendency to prioritise low-cost over high-cost errors (Gesiarz, Korn, & Sharot, 2019; Sharot & Garrett, 2016). While adaptive in volatile ancestral niches, such tendencies may misfire in modern contexts, a possibility highlighted by the mismatch hypothesis (Haselton et al., 2009). Even so, heuristics and biases often buffer cognition against uncertainty by simplifying complexity and prioritising cues of functional significance (Friston, 2010).

Together, these perspectives depict how perception and cognition can be cast as adaptive interfaces: compressed mappings that favour tractability and utility over fidelity, encoding fitness-relevant cues through bounded, heuristic, and cost-sensitive processes (Hoffman et al., 2015). Within Bayesian generative models, such biases can be reframed as structured consequences of priors, precision weighting, and update rules, rather than as arbitrary deviations from rationality (Lo & Zhang, 2021). This present analyses aims to clarify how and when departures from veridical inference may enhance survival utility under uncertainty (Trimmer et al., 2011).

2.7 Bayesian Inference, Predictive Processing, and the Free Energy Principle

Helmholtz's notion of "unconscious inference" captured the problem that cognition must solve: how to infer hidden causes from noisy sensory data. The Bayesian brain hypothesis proposes that the nervous system approximates Bayesian inference by combining prior expectations with likelihoods of current evidence to generate posterior beliefs about the world (Knill & Pouget, 2004; Griffiths et al., 2010; Friston, 2018). Formally, this relationship

can be summarised as Bayes rule: posterior \propto prior \times likelihood. Each posterior can serve recursively as the next prior, providing a computational benchmark for belief updating under uncertainty (Rescorla, 2024; Tenenbaum et al., 2011).

Predictive Processing develops this framework into a hierarchical model in which higher levels generate predictions and lower levels return mismatches as prediction errors. Crucially, prediction errors are not failures but the signals through which uncertainty is quantified and reduced. Their influence depends on precision weighting, which scales the impact of prediction errors relative to competing priors or sensory evidence (Clark, 2013). Attention has therefore been characterised as the selective allocation of precision to prediction error streams. This framing highlights that perception is not passive registration but an active process of hypothesis testing, producing simplified but functionally adequate models of the world (Friston, 2010; Hohwy, 2013).

The Free Energy Principle situates these ideas within a broader normative account. Organisms must maintain themselves within viable bounds despite uncertainty, and can be described as minimising variational free energy, a tractable measure of the mismatch between expectations and sensory states (Friston, 2010; Ramstead et al., 2018). In this sense, free energy minimisation links directly to entropy penalties: systems that reduce representational complexity while sustaining viability remain in low-surprisal states. The principle also frames the explore-exploit trade-off: expected free energy integrates extrinsic value (achieving fitness-relevant outcomes) with epistemic value (reducing uncertainty), showing how inference balances accuracy, utility, and adaptability over time (Friston et al., 2015).

Together, these frameworks cast cognition as recursive Bayesian updating constrained by precision and utility. This perspective motivates the present focus on how biased priors, entropy penalties, and coherence-preserving dynamics shape adaptive inference in volatile environments.

2.8 From Viability Constraints to Teleonomic Inference: A Synthesis

The preceding subsections (2.1–2.7) outlined how cognition is constructed rather than veridical, with Bayesian and predictive-processing formalisms describing *how* inference unfolds but leaving open the question of *why* particular priors and update rules take the forms they do. Addressing this “etiology gap” (Rescorla, 2024) requires recognising that priors emerge under evolutionary, developmental, and affective constraints, and that higher-order symbolic and identity-related priors can serve as long-term anchors of coherence. These considerations motivate a taxonomy of priors developed in §2.9, where the functional types implemented in the simulation are specified.

Within this framing, apparent “misrepresentations” acquire adaptive significance. Under bounded resources and asymmetric costs (see §2.5–2.6), systematic biases such as vigilance tilts, optimism effects, or conservatism reduce high-cost errors and enhance resilience. Predictive-processing and free-energy accounts tolerate such approximations, underscoring that the value of representation lies less in veridicality than in preserving viability under constraint. Motivated reasoning and confirmation bias illustrate this dynamic: agents often stabilise coherence by selectively crediting evidence that reduces existential or affective costs, a strategy that may appear epistemically irrational yet functions teleonomically as a resilience mechanism (Rigoli, 2022; Williams, 2021). This rationale underpins the inclusion of fitness payoff and relative advantage as external utility metrics,

alongside Coherence Stability Index (CSI) and KL divergence spikes as internal measures of representational stability.

A final implication concerns when beliefs should change. Coherence is not static preservation but stability-with-selective reorganisation: minor inconsistencies are typically absorbed, while larger perturbations trigger restructuring once accumulated error overwhelms the system (Varela, 1991; Dalege et al., 2024). At the theoretical level, identity has been described as a ‘hyperprior’ that anchors internal stability across multiple levels (Hohwy & Michael, 2020), making revision particularly costly when self-related or emotionally salient beliefs are involved. Although such dynamics are not explicitly modelled in the present simulation, their general logic informs the abstraction of coherence-sensitive modulation of belief updating and affective modulation.

Collectively, sections 2.1–2.7 justify a teleonomic reframing of Bayesian inference: accuracy and parsimony remain important, but they are subordinated to the broader aim of sustaining viability. Section 2.9 develops a taxonomy of priors, specifying the functional types operationalised in Agents A-D, while section 3 details how utilities, thresholds, and metrics implement this stance.

2.9 A Prior Taxonomy

To operationalise the priors implemented in the simulation, the present study adopts a functional taxonomy designed to provide a principled scaffold for agent architectures. On this axis, priors are understood not only as filters on evidence but also as regulators of trade-offs between efficiency, accuracy, and stability (see 2.8). Four functional types are instantiated in the simulation, mapping directly onto Agents A–D. Flat priors (Type I) provide a uniform

starting point and correspond to the idealised “as-if” observer benchmark (Geisler, 2010), reflected in Agent A, which treats all hypotheses as equally likely and therefore lacks structured bias. Conceptual priors (Type II) compress hypothesis spaces through schematic categories, thereby reducing complexity while introducing systematic biases consistent with Error Management Theory (Haselton & Nettle, 2006) and schema-driven generalisation (Katz et al., 2008; Shea, 2023). Agent B instantiates this type by privileging categorical distinctions. Affective priors (Type III) modulate evidence weighting according to valence and motivational salience, stabilising action policies even in the face of counterevidence (Barrett, 2017; Sharot & Garrett, 2016). Agent C reflects this class by biasing inference toward motivationally charged categories. Finally, Type IV priors regulate updating to preserve stability under volatile conditions, helping belief trajectories remain resilient despite perturbations (Moutoussis et al., 2014). Agent D embodied this class through a coherence-preserving prior that resisted unnecessary shifts yet remained responsive to persistent discrepancies, conserving stability while allowing flexible adaptation when required.

While the present simulation restricts its focus to this functional axis, a complementary etiological axis can also be specified. This axis classifies priors by their source and timescale of emergence, spanning phylogenetic hyperpriors shaped by evolutionary selection, ontogenetic priors tuned across the lifespan, and affective priors arising through state-dependent modulation. Higher-order symbolic and identity-related priors extend this taxonomy further, anchoring coherence across social and cultural timescales. Although theoretically important, these categories are not directly instantiated in the present simulation and are developed in Appendix C. For current purposes, the four functional types outlined above provide the conceptual foundation for testing how different prior structures influence inference under utility-relevant constraints.

3. Methods

3.1 Simulation Setup (Materials)

The modelling was implemented as an agent-based simulation in MATLAB R2025a, with DOI to custom scripts provided in Appendix B.5.5. The simulation materials consisted of virtual agents, Gaussian-distributed stimuli, payoff structures, and computational routines that generated and evaluated outcomes. Simulation-based methods were selected because they allow precise manipulation of latent variables and ecological contingencies that are difficult to isolate in human experiments, while also permitting stochastic repetition across random seeds to support robust statistical comparisons (Czégel et al., 2020; Farrell & Lewandowsky, 2018).

The task environment was a two-alternative forced-choice (2AFC) “threat vs non-threat” categorisation problem. On each trial, the latent category was sampled according to the block’s base rate (a Bernoulli process with probability p of threat). Threat stimuli were drawn from a Gaussian distribution with mean $+1.25$ and variance 1.0 , while non-threat stimuli were drawn from a distribution with mean -1.25 and variance 1.0 . To introduce ecological non-stationarity, the simulation alternated between three regimes: stable blocks with fixed category statistics, volatile blocks with hazard-driven state switches ($h = 1/80 \approx 0.0125$), and deceptive blocks in which category means were swapped mid-run. To capture sporadic sensory corruption, rare noise spikes were injected into the stimulus stream, occasionally flipping the perceived category independently of the true label; this corrupted stream drove the short prediction-error windows used in affective gating (Agent C) (Appendix B3).

Outcomes were evaluated using an asymmetric payoff matrix: +2 (hit), -2 (miss), +0.25 (correct rejection), -0.25 (false alarm), reflecting Error Management Theory (EMT), where the cost of missing a threat typically outweighs that of a false alarm (Haselton & Nettle, 2006). These utilities determined fitness payoffs and oracle benchmarks; in the simulation runs, agents applied a fixed symmetric threshold ($\tau = 0.5$) for decisions (see Appendix B3.4).

Controlled constants ensured comparability across agents, with fitness scaling term ($\beta = 2.0$, weights ecological payoffs) and entropy/precision penalty ($\delta = 0.1$), used in Agent D's update dynamics. Both parameters entered the agents' update rules as fitness- and entropy-weighted scalings of learning rate and representational cost (see Appendix B). In practice, δ influenced update scaling most strongly in the adaptive agent (D), but was held constant across all agents for comparability.

Each run comprised 1,000 trials partitioned into unequal regimes: stable (100 trials), volatile (500), and deceptive (50), with the remaining trials allocated to transition/buffer segments used only for plotting. Because regime lengths differ, payoff and relative advantage are reported as absolute totals within each regime and are interpreted within-regime (i.e., between agents under the same volatility condition), not across regimes. Where cross-regime comparisons are made, per-trial summaries are provided in Table A2, Appendix A. Pilot testing indicated that 40 seeds were sufficient to stabilise standard error estimates, and 50 random seeds matched across agents were therefore adopted to provide additional margin. This setup established a replicable environment that combined ambiguous evidence, asymmetric costs, and ecological non-stationarity to provide a principled baseline for evaluating agent architectures. The shared generative assumptions, payoff structure, and

constants across agents are illustrated in Figure 2, which also outlines the agent-specific priors and update rules.

3.2 Design

The simulation employed a fully specified, reproducible design that manipulated task ecology and agent architecture while holding constants fixed (see 3.1). Each random seed generated an identical stimulus sequence and regime schedule shared across agents, allowing within-seed paired comparisons that isolate architecture effects from stochastic variation. Because regime lengths differed (stable = 100, volatile = 500, deceptive = 50), outcome totals are interpreted within-regime (see Section 3.1). Independent variables included agent class with four levels (A–D: flat-prior baseline, schema-biased, affect-modulated, coherence-sensitive adaptive), environmental regime with three levels (stable, volatile, deceptive), hazard rate ($h = 1/80 \approx 0.0125$) which set the probability of an environmental switch on each trial; and signal discriminability (Δ , the separation of class means, here, defined as: $\Delta = \text{in } 1.25$ in the baseline configuration ($\mu_T = +1.25$, $\mu_N = -1.25$), which determined the degree of overlap (sensory ambiguity) between the threat and non-threat distributions. Three targeted probes further tested inference dynamics: ecological base-rate disparity (p , proportion of threat trials in a block), which skewed category frequencies, schema-bias strength (γT , prior exponent applied once at Agent B’s initialisation; section 3.4); and gain-mapping parameters for Agent D (λ -bounds, α_{base} , max_step). Full parameter values are provided in Appendix B1.

Together with the asymmetric payoff matrix (used to evaluate outcomes and define oracle benchmarks), these manipulations provided a controlled stress test of how agents balanced payoff, coherence, and adaptability under ecological uncertainty. Dependent

variables were summarised along four pre-specified performance families: epistemic fit, fitness utility, coherence stability, and adaptive efficiency. Full metric definitions are presented in section 3.5 and equations Appendix B. Controls ensured comparability across agents: default parameters (β , δ , trial length) were held constant unless explicitly manipulated, and matched random seeds eliminated stochastic differences in input histories. Bootstrap resampling and targeted sensitivity analyses confirmed that results did not depend on a narrow set of parameter choices. These practices, combined with the within-seed design, ensured interpretability and replicability.

3.3 Procedure

All simulations were ran using the materials and factors described in sections 3.1–3.2. For each condition, agents were initialised with their fixed constants (β , δ) and condition-specific values (γT), and a regime schedule was generated according to block type: stable with fixed category statistics, volatile with hazard-driven state switches, or deceptive with mid-block mean swaps. A single random seed produced the full regime schedule and stimulus sequence, matched across agents so that each class experienced the same trial history. Trial-wise updating was used to mirror the structure of perceptual categorisation tasks and to allow hazard-driven changes to directly shape belief dynamics.

Each run comprised 1,000 trials. On each trial, a latent category was sampled from the current regime, a stimulus was drawn from the corresponding Gaussian distribution, and presented to all agents. Agents updated beliefs via their class-specific inference rule, issued a categorical response, and received utility according to the payoff matrix. Logged variables included posteriors (for entropy and KL calculations), responses, correctness, and fitness payoffs. After 1,000 trials, run-level summaries such as cumulative payoff and relative

advantage were computed. Each condition was replicated across 50 independent seeds, and arrays were concatenated across seeds to generate the data structures used in inferential analyses.

3.4 Agent Specifications

Four agent classes were implemented to provide a graded test of inference enrichments under the same task ecology. All agents shared the same Gaussian generative assumptions, payoff structure and decision rule, differing only in prior specification and update dynamics. Figure 2 provides a schematic overview of the four agents, highlighting their shared Bayesian components alongside their distinctive priors and update mechanisms. All agents used a fixed symmetric decision threshold ($\tau = 0.5$) to ensure comparability across architectures. This design isolated the influence of specific priors and update rules, embedding utility sensitivity within learning dynamics (via β and δ) rather than solely in decision choice. Definitions of formal equations, symbols and parameterisations are provided in Appendix B.

Agent A, the flat-prior Bayesian observer, served as the baseline. It began each run with a uniform prior over categories, updating beliefs by Bayesian conditioning providing the accuracy-oriented benchmark against which enriched variants were compared. Since the prior was fixed at 0.5, and updated only by standard Bayesian conditioning, Agent A lacks any mechanism for adaptive precision adjustment.

Agent B instantiated a schema-based vigilance prior by exponentiating the initial threat probability with γ_T (γ_N for non-threat), producing a categorical tilt toward threat at the outset. This generated a vigilance-biased schema that was conservatively maintained across

trials, allowing only minor drift, effectively functioning as a static schema for the remainder of the run. Such miscalibrated vigilance priors are consistent with EMT (Haselton & Nettle, 2006).

Unlike Agent B's schema bias, Agent C started on a neutral prior (0.5) and introduced state-dependent affective modulation of threat probability. On each trial, a valence term (based on the recent 20-trial proportion of threats) and a non-linear 'affective surprise' signal jointly pushed the prior toward threat. This target bias was then combined with a baseline offset and updated via an exponential decay rule, ensuring bounded adjustments within [0.05, 0.95]. As a result, C's prior could drift conservatively under low salience and become more threat-biased under high salience, while the likelihood model and decision thresholds remained unchanged (see Appendix B for formal specification).

Agent D did not apply the affective gain; instead, it coupled a conservative prior (~ 0.30) with a Teleonomic Bayesian (TBI) inspired update that balances fitness gains against representational costs. On each trial, a TBI score, combining expected utility (weighted by β) with an entropy-based penalty (scaled by δ) and a small step-cost – was mapped through a logistic to produce a multiplicative gain $\lambda t_{bi} \in [\lambda \min, \lambda \max]$. The effective learning rate was then $\alpha_{eff} = \lambda t_{bi} \cdot \alpha_{base}$, applied to a leak-damped update toward the current posterior; ($\kappa t \in [0.5, 0.95]$), with a soft momentum term to preserve direction when evidence is consistent. A hard step clamp (`max_step`) limited abrupt changes. Together, the entropy-weighted TBI gain, leak/momentum, and step clamp implement a coherence-preserving policy: updates are conservative when evidence is ambiguous yet scale up efficiently when utility-relevant discrepancies accumulate, yielding stable beliefs without sacrificing adaptability.

Figure 2.

Schematic overview of shared simulation elements and agent-specific priors and update rules (Agents A–D)

The four agents thus formed a graded sequence from neutral inference through schematic vigilance bias and affective calibration to adaptive, coherence-preserving. By holding generative assumptions constant and varying only prior structures and update dynamics, performance differences could be attributed directly to the targeted modelling ingredients.

3.5 Metrics

Agent performance was assessed across four complementary dimensions: epistemic fit, instrumental utility, coherence stability, and adaptive efficiency (Table 1). This multidimensional framework ensured evaluation did not rely solely on accuracy but captured how agents balanced fidelity, payoffs, stability, and flexibility. Formal definitions and equations are provided in Appendix B.5; here we outline their operationalisation and interpretive focus. Figures of metric results (section 4) were produced in MATLAB from simulation outputs.

Epistemic fit indexed how closely posterior beliefs tracked the true state. Accuracy, the proportion of correct classifications, provided a baseline measure of inference quality. Area under the ROC curve (AUC) assessed discrimination ability independently of threshold setting, while the Brier score quantified calibration by penalising over- or underconfident probability estimates. Root mean square error (RMSE) captured the RMSE between agent's posterior and the oracle posterior, with Transient RMSE added to characterise short-term error spikes following regime shifts. Accuracy and AUC were analysed per block type (stable, volatile, deceptive) to reflect context sensitivity, whereas RMSE, Transient RMSE,

and Brier were summarised globally to capture aggregate predictive fidelity (Burnham & Anderson, 2002).

Instrumental utility evaluated whether decisions maximised survival-weighted outcomes. Fitness payoff (U_t) was computed as the cumulative reward from the asymmetric payoff matrix. Relative advantage indexed utility efficiency by benchmarking each agent's realised payoff U_t^{realised} against an oracle benchmark U_t^{oracle} . The oracle posterior was computed from the true generative base rate, using the same fixed symmetric threshold ($\tau = 0.5$) applied to all agents, ensuring comparability. Relative advantage was thus defined as the difference between oracle and realised cumulative payoffs, summed across trials. Lower values indicate greater efficiency in converting information into survival-weighted utility, with negative values possible when stochastic outcomes yield payoffs exceeding the oracle baseline. Totals reflect “budget utility” over the exposure of each regime. Given unequal regime lengths, between-regime totals are not directly comparable; inferential tests for payoff/advantage are therefore framed within regime and within seed. Both measures were analysed per block type to reflect ecological contingencies and then aggregated globally for direct comparison of architectures (Geisler, 2003).

Finally, a Coherence Stability Index (CSI) was operationalised to index coherence; how reliably agents maintained precise belief states. On each trial, coherence stability was indexed using a moving posterior variance v_t (window w) and an exponentially smoothed accuracy trace a_t with smoothing constant δ^{EMA} . Reported CSI values are the mean across trials within a block. Higher CSI values indicate greater representational stability when accuracy is sustained. Formal definitions are provided in Appendix B.5.3. For complementarity, we also counted “KL spikes,” to measure coherence disruptions, defined as

instances where the Kullback–Leibler divergence between successive posteriors exceeded a spike threshold of 0.05 (see Appendix B.5.3).

Adaptive efficiency assessed how agents balanced responsiveness with stability. A precision-adaptivity cost index ($\Sigma\Delta\pi$) accumulated the absolute magnitude of trial-wise changes in the prior probability of threat, across trials, thereby operationalising $\Delta\pi$ as the step-to-step adjustment of the prior. $\Sigma|\Delta\pi|$ therefore captures the cumulative magnitude of prior drift in response to evidence – effectively indexing how much an agent’s belief baseline moves around over time. The metric is termed “precision–adaptivity” because it serves as a proxy for the stability–flexibility trade-off: frequent or large swings in π_t imply greater volatility and thus higher adaptivity cost. This was computed globally to provide a measure of each agent’s overall balance between stability and flexibility. By design, Agent A maintains a flat prior with fixed precision and does not update π_t ; consequently, its adaptivity cost is identically zero. RMSE also contributed here, capturing transition errors in posterior updating during regime shifts. Together, these metrics provided a structured performance profile: accuracy and AUC reflected baseline fidelity, payoff and relative advantage indexed ecological success, CSI and KL spikes traced coherence dynamics, and RMSE with $\Sigma\Delta\pi$ captured stability–flexibility. By combining per-block and global analyses, the evaluation distinguished context-sensitive differences from architecture-wide trends.

Table 1

Summary of performance metrics, their operational definitions, and interpretive focus across the four evaluation dimensions.

Dimension Assessed	Metric	Description	Interpretation Focus
Epistemic Fit	Accuracy	Proportion of correct threat/non-threat classifications.	Baseline inference quality.
	AUC	Area under ROC curve across classification thresholds.	Discrimination ability.
	RMSE	Root mean square error between predicted and realised outcomes.	Overall predictive error.
	Transient RMSE	Mean predictive error within ± 15 trials of regime shifts.	Sensitivity to sudden environmental change
	Brier Score	Mean squared error of probabilistic predictions.	Calibration of confidence.
Instrumental Utility	Fitness Payoff	Cumulative reward points from correct classifications weighted by payoff matrix.	Overall task success / utility yield.
	Relative Advantage	Oracle–achieved payoff difference summed over trials (posterior–Bayes oracle at $\tau = 0.5$ – realised).	How efficiently agents convert information into survival-weighted utility relative to a common baseline.
Coherence Stability	CSI	Coherence Stability Index: inverse-variance-weighted accuracy from posterior trajectories.	Stability of belief states. (Higher values = more stability)
	KL Spikes	Count of KL divergence > 0.05 between successive posteriors.	Frequency of coherence disruptions.
Adaptive Efficiency	Precision-Adaptivity Cost ($\Sigma\Delta\pi$)	Cumulative magnitude of prior adjustments	Proxy for stability-flexibility trade-off in inference.

3.6 Statistical Analysis

Analyses followed a within-seed paired design, with each agent class (A–D) evaluated against identical stimulus sequences and regime schedules. This controlled for stochastic variability and ensured observed differences reflected agent architecture rather than environmental noise. Descriptive uncertainty was quantified using paired bootstrap bias-corrected and accelerated (BCa) 95% confidence intervals, computed with 10,000 resamples. Inferential analyses were conducted within a Bayesian framework, employing paired-samples t-tests as implemented in JASP. Bayes factors were computed using the default Cauchy prior on standardised effect sizes ($r = 0.707$), centred on zero. This prior reflects the assumption that most plausible effects are small-to-medium in size, while still assigning lower probability to large effects. Directional hypotheses were specified by truncating the prior distribution to one tail (e.g., $D > A$ for payoff, $D < A$ for relative advantage), ensuring that alternatives reflected the prior expectations. Robustness of the conclusions was assessed by repeating tests under wider priors ($r = 1.0$ and $r = 1.5$), allowing evaluation of sensitivity to prior specification.

Psychologically, the prior is not a belief about participants but a distribution over possible effect sizes (Cohen's d), centered on the null value of zero. Thus, evidence ratios (Bayes factors) quantify how much more likely the observed data are under the specified alternative than under the null, assuming equal prior odds. They provide a graded measure of relative support rather than binary confirmation (Lee & Wagenmakers, 2014). Assumptions for paired comparisons (normality of difference scores) were inspected visually and showed no serious violations. Homogeneity of variance was not required due to the within-seed paired design. Outlier inspection did not indicate problematic cases.

Hypotheses were prespecified to minimise post-hoc bias. Specifically: H1 predicted that enriched agents (B–D) would achieve higher global cumulative payoffs than the flat-prior baseline (A). H2 predicted that the adaptive agent (D) would minimise global relative advantage (oracle – achieved payoff difference; lower = better). H3a predicted that enriched agents would maintain greater coherence stability specifically during volatile blocks, with Agent D expected to show the highest CSI. H3b predicted that Agent D would generate fewer global KL divergence spikes (coherence disruptions) across the full task compared to other agents. These procedures provided a transparent and reproducible framework for evaluating performance differences across agent classes, while maintaining sensitivity to uncertainty and prior specification.

3.7 Sensitivity, Robustness, and Ablation Analyses

A series of supplementary analyses was conducted to assess whether performance differences reflected stable properties of the agent architectures rather than artefacts of parameterisation or stochastic noise. Sensitivity analyses were carried out using both structured one-way grid analyses, two-way interaction sweeps and Latin hypercube sampling (LHS), varying key parameters such as β , δ , and hazard rates across wide ranges. These procedures served to evaluate whether model behaviour was contingent on narrow settings or generalised across parameter spaces.

Robustness was further examined through seed-wise distributions, bootstrap confidence intervals, and the recomputation of Bayes factors under alternative prior widths, providing checks on the stability of inferences under stochastic variation and prior specification. Edge-case analyses were also included to evaluate behaviour under conditions such as extreme volatility, altered payoff symmetries, and manipulated separability, thereby

probing the ecological plausibility of the models outside canonical task conditions. Similarly, ablation analyses were implemented by selectively disabling the gain and updating component components of Agent D, allowing the contributions of coherence-preserving updating elements to be isolated. Finally, convergence diagnostics were applied to track posterior dynamics, confirming that model trajectories stabilised as expected and that disruptions following regime shifts remained recoverable. Full procedural details are reported in Appendix C.

4. Results

Raw global descriptives (Table A1) and global cumulative plots (Figure A1) are provided in Appendix A. Summary descriptive statistics for all performance metrics are presented in Table 1. Simulation outcomes were evaluated across ten indices (see Section 3.5 for details), spanning epistemic fit, instrumental utility, coherence stability, and adaptive efficiency. Analyses were conducted within a Bayesian paired design using default Cauchy priors, with Bayes factors providing graded evidence for pre-specified hypotheses. To assess ecological validity, results were stratified by environmental regime (stable, volatile, deceptive). Because regime lengths differ (stable = 100 trials, volatile = 500, deceptive = 50), totals are interpreted within regime; any cross-regime comparisons use per-trial means; see Appendix A (Tables A2-A3). At an aggregate level, payoff followed $D > C > A > B$, while Relative Advantage followed $D < C \ll A, B$ (H1–H2). Agent D also showed higher CSI in volatile blocks than other agents (H3a) and fewer global coherence disruptions following regime shifts (H3b).

4.1 Descriptive Statistics and Visualisations

Results are presented in two parts. Section 4.1.1 reports prerespecified outcomes – fitness payoff, relative advantage, coherence stability (CSI), and coherence disruptions (KL spikes) – which provide the basis for hypothesis tests (H1-H3b). Section 4.1.2 reports exploratory outcomes, including accuracy, AUC, calibration measures (Brier score, RMSE, transient RMSE), and precision-adaptivity cost, which offer convergent evidence on inference quality and update dynamics. Descriptive statistics are summarised in Tables 2-4, with visualisations shown in Figures 1-3; supplementary global comparisons are provided in Appendix A (Figure A1/Table A1).

4.1.1 Hypothesis-specific Metrics

Table 3 reports descriptive outcomes stratified by block regime for payoff, relative advantage, CSI, and KL spikes. Payoff values were highest in volatile blocks, with Agents C and D achieving greater totals than Agents A and B. Note that volatile totals are larger primarily because the volatile block is longer; the ordering of agents within volatility ($D \gtrsim C \gg A, B$) is the substantive result. Relative Advantage also varied across regimes, with Agent D showing the lowest (best) values overall, followed by Agent C, and higher values for baseline agents (lower = better; values can be negative). CSI values showed regime-dependent variation; because CSI is an inverse-variance-weighted accuracy index (higher = more stable), Agent D exhibited the highest CSI in volatile blocks, indicating more stable beliefs under change. KL spikes were most frequent under volatility, with Agents A and B exhibiting higher disruption counts than hierarchical agents. Figure 3 provides block-stratified descriptives for payoff, CSI, and KL spikes, allowing performance to be visualised across stable, volatile, and deceptive regimes. These descriptives offer context for the global inferential tests that follow, and in the case of CSI (H3a), provide the basis for testing

volatility-specific stability. Importantly, while these descriptives are presented stratified by block, inferential tests were conducted on global cumulative measures for H1 (payoff), H2 (relative advantage), and H3b (KL spikes), whereas H3a (CSI) was tested specifically within volatile blocks. Global contrasts are provided in Appendix A (Figure A1).

Table 3

Performance metrics; M (SD), across regimes (stable, volatile, deceptive). Totals are regime-wise sums; do not compare magnitudes across regimes because block lengths differ. Values support within-regime contrasts between agents. N = 50 seeds per condition

Metric	Regime	Agent A	Agent B	Agent C	Agent D
Payoff	Stable	206.305 (20.975)	193.365 (21.771)	215.205 (26.151)	218.035 (22.710)
	Volatile	877.180 (29.930)	848.910 (32.004)	1046.740 (21.961)	1057.510 (24.390)
	Deceptive	0.590 (9.955)	1.480 (9.579)	10.500 (12.513)	13.170 (10.659)
Relative Advantage	Stable	-0.440 (1.339)	12.500 (7.837)	-9.340 (14.164)	-12.170 (8.571)
	Volatile	185.760 (26.786)	214.030 (26.677)	16.200 (10.766)	5.430 (12.585)
	Deceptive	0.010 (0.071)	-0.880 (4.759)	-9.900 (8.678)	-12.570 (5.999)
CSI	Stable	0.791 (0.028)	0.773 (0.031)	0.742 (0.037)	0.713 (0.038)
	Volatile	1.283 (0.086)	1.315 (0.096)	2.320 (0.425)	3.651 (1.801)
	Deceptive	0.472 (0.053)	0.469 (0.054)	0.494 (0.088)	0.513 (0.083)
Spikes	Stable	186.200 (7.597)	186.320 (7.776)	180.800 (8.866)	184.400 (8.154)
	Volatile	469.440 (15.639)	460.740 (16.103)	346.580 (18.967)	333.200 (22.693)
	Deceptive	46.060 (3.254)	46.120 (3.081)	43.920 (4.020)	43.820 (3.212)

Figure 3.

Mean outcomes across regimes (stable, volatile, deceptive). Panels show cumulative fitness payoff, Coherence Stability Index (CSI), and coherence disruptions (KL spikes). Bars show regime-wise totals; interpret within regime only. Cross-regime per-trial means are provided in Appendix A (Table A2-A3)

4.1.2 Exploratory Metrics

Exploratory outcomes are summarised in Table 2, with block-wise comparisons visualised for Accuracy, AUC, and Precision–Adaptivity Cost (Figure 4). Accuracy and AUC were highest in stable and volatile blocks and declined under deceptive conditions. Across all regimes, Agents C and D had higher values than Agents A and B. Calibration indices were assessed globally. RMSE and Brier scores were lower for Agents C and D compared with Agents A and B. Transient RMSE values were higher for Agents C and D than for Agents A and B, showing larger short-term error spikes following regime shifts. Precision–Adaptivity Cost ($\Sigma\Delta\pi$) reflected the cumulative magnitude of precision adjustments across trials, where Agent A had a value of 0.000, reflecting its design as a non-adaptive baseline with no precision

updating. Agent B had a small adjustment cost whereas Agents C and D showed larger adjustment magnitudes, with Agent C highest and Agent D lower.

Figure 4.

Bars show regime-wise averages for indices bounded between 0-1 (Accuracy, AUC) and cumulative totals for Precision-Adaptivity Cost; interpret within regime only

Table 2

Summary descriptive statistics; M (SD), for exploratory metrics across agents (N = 50 seeds each). Accuracy, ROC AUC, RMSE, and Brier are per-trial indices, whereas Precision–Adaptivity Cost reflects a cumulative adjustment magnitude summed across the task

Exploratory Metrics	Agent A	Agent B	Agent C	Agent D
Accuracy	0.860 (0.010)	0.844 (0.011)	0.876 (0.012)	0.880 (0.011)
ROC AUC	0.917 (0.009)	0.919 (0.009)	0.923 (0.009)	0.927 (0.009)
Precision–Adaptivity Cost	0.000 (0.000)	0.872 (0.073)	20.930 (1.975)	5.438 (0.206)
RMSE	0.165 (0.006)	0.154 (0.006)	0.140 (0.012)	0.129 (0.009)
Transient RMSE	0.172 (0.013)	0.173 (0.014)	0.241 (0.023)	0.236 (0.021)
Brier Score	0.106 (0.007)	0.103 (0.007)	0.096 (0.008)	0.093 (0.007)

4.2 Hypothesis-Driven Analyses

Bayesian paired-samples t-tests evaluated the hypotheses (see Section 3.6 for analytic details). Results are expressed as Bayes factors (BF_{10}), which quantify relative evidence for the alternative compared to the null, with subscripts denoting support for the alternative over the null (van Doorn et al., 2021). Values greater than 1 indicate increasing evidence for the alternative, while values below 1 indicate evidence for the null. Robustness was assessed across wider prior widths.

4.2.1 H1: Fitness Payoff

The first hypothesis predicted that hierarchical agents would secure higher cumulative payoffs than baselines, with Agent D expected to achieve the greatest advantage. Table 4 summarises global descriptive statistics, with the ordering following $D > C > A > B$. Figure

A2 (Appendix A) shows the descriptive contrasts ($\pm 95\%$ CI). Bayesian paired t-tests supported this pattern, providing decisive evidence for $C > A$ ($BF_{10} = 1.90 \times 10^{39}$) and $D > A$ ($BF_{10} = 2.99 \times 10^{41}$), as well as strong evidence for $A > B$ ($BF_{10} = 9.84 \times 10^7$). Robustness checks across prior widths (Appendix A; Figure A3) confirmed stability for the C-A and D-A contrasts. For the A-B comparison, evidence was decisive under the default prior but less robust under ultrawide priors. Distributional diagnostics (Appendix A; Figure A4) indicated that seed-wise paired differences were approximately normally distributed for A-B and A-C, with mild deviations in the tails for A-D. Thus, under equal prior odds, the data were 2.99×10^{41} times more likely if Agent D $>$ A, 1.90×10^{39} times more likely if C $>$ A, and 9.84×10^7 times more likely if A $>$ B, than under the respective nulls.

Table 4

Cumulative descriptive statistics for fitness payoff across agents ($N = 50$ seeds each). Means are reported with standard deviations (SD), standard errors (SE), and 95% confidence intervals

Agent	Mean	SD	SE	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper
A	1084.08	43.20	6.11	1072.10	1096.05
B	1043.76	46.99	6.65	1030.73	1056.78
C	1272.45	41.16	5.82	1261.04	1283.85
D	1288.72	41.12	5.82	1277.32	1300.11

4.2.2 H2: Relative Advantage

The second hypothesis predicted that hierarchical updating would minimise global relative advantage (oracle – achieved; lower = better). Descriptives are reported in Table 5, showing the ordering was $D < C \ll A, B$. Figure A5 (Appendix A) shows the descriptive contrasts ($\pm 95\%$ CI). Bayesian tests supported this pattern with decisive evidence that relative advantage was lower for D; $D < A$ ($BF_{10} = 1.44 \times 10^{39}$), $D < B$ ($BF_{10} = 1.27 \times 10^{43}$), and $D < C$ ($BF_{10} = 2.81 \times 10^4$). Robustness checks across prior widths (Appendix Figure A6) confirmed that these findings were stable, with Bayes factors consistently above decisive thresholds. Distributional diagnostics (Appendix Figure A7) indicated that seed-wise paired differences were approximately normally distributed overall, with mild negative skew evident for the A-B comparison and slight upper-tail deviation for A-C. The A-D distribution was closest to normality. Thus, under equal prior odds, the data were 1.44×10^{39} times more likely if $D < A$, 1.27×10^{43} times more likely if $D < B$, and 2.81×10^4 times more likely if $D < C$, than under the respective nulls.

Table 5

Cumulative descriptive statistics for relative advantage (lower = better; can be negative) across agents ($N = 50$ seeds each). Means are reported with standard deviations (SD), standard errors (SE), and 95% confidence intervals

Agent	Mean	SD	SE	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper
A	185.33	26.84	3.80	177.89	192.77
B	225.65	27.32	3.86	218.08	233.22
C	-3.04	18.35	2.60	-8.13	2.05
D	-19.31	16.34	2.31	-23.84	-14.78

4.2.3 H3a: Coherence Stability

The third hypothesis predicted that Agent D would show higher CSI (greater stability) in volatile blocks compared to other agents. Descriptive statistics are reported in Table 6, showing the ordering; $D > C > B \approx A$. Figure A8 (Appendix A) shows the descriptive contrasts ($\pm 95\%$ CI). Directional Bayesian tests provided decisive evidence that CSI was higher for D; $D > A$ ($BF_{10} = 1.95 \times 10^{10}$), $D > B$ ($BF_{10} = 1.47 \times 10^{10}$), and $D > C$ ($BF_{10} = 3.64 \times 10^5$). Robustness checks (Appendix Figure A9) indicated Bayes factors remained large across wide and ultrawide priors. Seed-wise paired differences (Appendix Figure A10) showed approximate normality in Q-Q plots, though histograms indicated departures from a symmetric Gaussian, particularly for A-D. Mild lower-tail skew was evident for A-C and A-D. Thus, under equal prior odds, the data were 1.95×10^{10} times more likely if $D > A$, 1.47×10^{10} times more likely if $D > B$, and 3.64×10^5 times more likely if $D > C$, than under the respective nulls.

Table 6

Descriptive statistics for coherence stability (CSI) across agents in volatile blocks ($N = 50$ seeds each). Means are reported with standard deviations (SD), standard errors (SE), and 95% confidence intervals

Agent	Mean	SD	SE	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper
A	1.283	0.086	0.012	1.259	1.307
B	1.315	0.096	0.014	1.287	1.342
C	2.320	0.425	0.060	2.199	2.441
D	3.651	1.801	0.255	3.139	4.163

4.2.4 H3b: Coherence Disruptions

The final hypothesis predicted that Agent D would generate fewer coherence disruptions (lower KL spike counts) following regime shifts compared to other agents. Descriptive statistics are reported in Table 7, with ordering $D < C < B < A$. Descriptive contrasts are shown in Appendix Figure A11 (\pm 95% CI). Bayesian paired-samples tests indicated decisive evidence for $D < A$ ($BF_{10} = 6.75 \times 10^{43}$) and $D < B$ ($BF_{10} = 6.48 \times 10^{43}$). For the D–C comparison, evidence was also strong in favour of $D < C$ ($BF_{10} = 6.92 \times 10^4$). Robustness checks (Appendix Figure A12) showed that Bayes factors for all three contrasts remained large across wide and ultrawide priors and ultrawide priors. Seed-wise paired differences (Appendix Figure A13) showed approximate normality in Q–Q plots, with only mild skew evident for the D-A and D-B distributions. Histograms further indicated a slight departure from Gaussian symmetry for D-C, consistent with greater variance across seeds. Thus, under equal prior odds, the data were 6.75×10^{43} times more likely if $D < A$, 6.48×10^{43} times more likely if $D < B$, and 6.92×10^4 times more likely if $D < C$ than under the respective nulls.

Table 7

Descriptive statistics for coherence disruptions (KL spike counts) across agents, cumulative across the run ($N = 50$ seeds each). Means are reported with standard deviations (SD), standard errors (SE), and 95% confidence intervals

Agent	Mean	SD	SE	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper
A	704.12	15.68	2.22	699.77	708.47
B	695.58	16.36	2.31	691.05	700.11
C	573.44	20.54	2.90	567.75	579.13
D	563.50	24.81	3.51	556.62	570.38

4.3 Robustness, Sensitivity, and Ablation Results

Supplementary analyses reported in Appendix C (Tables C1–C7; Figures C1–C10) confirmed that the principal findings were not dependent on narrow parameter settings or stochastic artefacts. Sensitivity analyses (Table C1; Figure C3) demonstrated that fitness varied systematically with β across hazard conditions, while relative advantage, coherence stability, and KL spike counts remained within stable ranges. Manipulations of hazard rate (Tables C2–C3; Figure C4) showed predictable reductions in coherence stability and increases in KL spikes under greater volatility, while overall fitness levels were preserved, supporting the use of an intermediate hazard rate ($h = 1/80$) in the main simulations. Manipulations of entropy cost (Table C6; Figure C9) further indicated that the δ parameter exerted minimal influence on outcomes, consistent with expectations. Edge-case analyses (Table C6; Figures C7–C10) showed that extreme volatility and reduced separability degraded performance across all agents, but trajectories remained consistent and recoverable across seeds. Heatmaps (Figures C8–C10) confirmed that outcomes followed smooth and interpretable patterns across the parameter space.

Complementary operationalisations (Figures C1–C2) confirmed that results were not dependent on a single metric definition. These converging results indicate that coherence stability and disruption indices were robust to differences in measurement. Convergence diagnostics (Figure C6) provided further validation that posterior dynamics behaved as expected across architectures. Disruption indices such as KL peak and KL AUC per change (Figures C1–C2) showed transient error spikes following regime shifts, but distributions were bounded and recovered consistently across seeds, indicating that posterior trajectories stabilised after environmental transitions.

Robustness checks based on seed-wise comparisons (Figure C6; Tables C4–C5; Figure C5) further supported the stability of results. Across multiple seeds, performance differences between agents were consistent, and KL spike thresholds varied between 0.02 and 0.10 yielded convergent patterns, confirming that the choice of threshold did not bias outcomes. Ablation analyses (Table C7) isolated the contributions of Agent D’s adaptive mechanisms. When gain modulation was disabled (“Gain-off”), fitness and relative advantage declined and coherence variability increased, whereas disabling the update pathway (“Update-off”) preserved fitness but altered adaptive efficiency. These comparisons demonstrated that the gain and update pathways each contributed distinct aspects of performance.

Finally, Latin Hypercube Sampling (Table C5) extended these checks by jointly perturbing multiple parameters rather than varying them in isolation. Results averaged across seeds and samples showed stable relative patterns across agents, with no evidence that simultaneous parameter variation altered the overall conclusions. This supports the generalisability of the findings beyond narrow parameter ranges. Collectively, these results confirm that the reported outcomes were stable across parameter perturbations, measurement alternatives, seed resampling, and architectural variants. These procedures validate the consistency of the simulation results under a wide range of conditions.

Figure 4

Alternative operationalisations of coherence stability and post-shift disruption. Top row: coherence stability indexed by raw variance, normalised variance, and spike-trimmed variance of CSI during stable blocks. Bottom row: post-shift disruption indexed by spike count, KL divergence area, and posterior-variance stability

5. Discussion

Across regimes, the simulation compared how Bayesian agents balance utility, relative advantage, and representational stability. A consistent pattern emerged: the coherence-sensitive hierarchical agent (D) showed the strongest payoff and relative advantage profile (lower = better) with lower coherence variability than non-hierarchical baselines; the affect-modulated hierarchical agent (C) performed intermediately; the flat-prior baseline (A) exceeded the schema-biased categorical agent (B). These outcomes broadly supported the hypotheses (H1-H3b). We next interpret these patterns in relation to the prespecified hypotheses, situate them within existing theory, and critically evaluate their scope and limitations, before outlining directions for empirical testing.

5.1.2 H1: Payoff gains with enriched priors

Across regimes, progressively enriched priors were associated with higher fitness payoffs than the flat-prior baseline, though the mechanisms differed. The apparent order-of-magnitude differences in total payoff reflect regime lengths (volatile blocks contained more trials), not differences in per-trial efficiency; agent orderings ($D > C > A > B$) remained the same when values were normalised per trial, see Appendix A (Figure A2). Agent A, serving as the flat Gaussian baseline, provided no asymmetries. Agent B added a schema-biased vigilance prior yet its miscalibration inflated false alarms and yielded lower payoffs than A, reflecting EMT's prediction that vigilance priors can become maladaptive when tuned too strongly toward false-alarm avoidance, inflating costs under balanced environments (Haselton & Nettle, 2006). Agent C improved on this by incorporating affective modulation: interoceptive states amplified threat-consistent evidence, producing higher payoffs at the cost of reduced flexibility under volatility. Here, EMT dynamics were evident: weighting toward high-salience evidence improved threat detection but reduced the capacity to recalibrate when environments shifted (Haselton & Nettle, 2006). This pattern also echoes findings on optimism bias, where affective weighting systematically tilts inference toward desirable outcomes (Sharot & Garrett, 2016). Agent D's neutral start and entropy-weighted gain with bounded updates enabled regulated belief revision that was conservative in stable contexts but adaptive under change, producing the strongest overall advantage under the fixed decision criterion.

These outcomes were broadly consistent with expectations, that enriched priors agents (C) would outperform baselines, and that Agent D would achieve the most balanced profile. Converging exploratory indices supported this interpretation: both C and D were associated with higher accuracy and AUC, and lower Brier and RMSE scores (Table 2; Fig. 3),

suggesting that payoff advantages did not come at the expense of calibration or discrimination quality. At the same time, C's higher precision-adaptivity cost highlighted a resource trade-off, whereas D achieved a more efficient balance across utility, accuracy, and stability.

5.1.3 H2: Relative Advantage minimisation

Agent D showed the smallest relative advantage values (oracle – achieved; lower = better, with negatives possible), leaving the least utility gap relative to the posterior-based oracle benchmark (using the same symmetric threshold as all agents). Both hierarchical agents (C and D) reduced the utility gap compared to the baselines (A and B), consistent with the hypothesis that relative advantage would be lowest for agents could flexibly recalibrate under volatility. While Agent D achieved this through its gain-modulated update schedule – entropy weighting and bounded adjustments that dampened updates under low volatility but scaled adaptation upward when discrepancies persisted – Agent C also benefited from its affective modulation of precision, whereby valence and surprise terms weighted evidence more heavily when outcomes carried greater affective significance. This likely contributed to its reduced relative advantage, even though the absence of entropy-based smoothing its adjustments were sharper and more categorical, in contrast to D's more graded, gain-modulated adaptation. This pattern aligns with bounded-rationality and satisficing accounts, which emphasise how adaptive success lies not in achieving global optimality but in minimising costly shortfalls under uncertainty by deploying efficient, good-enough strategies within ecological constraints (Simon, 1956; Gigerenzer, 2002). Agent D's policy mirrors threshold-based models of belief revision, which constrain change until adaptive bounds are exceeded, and predictive-processing accounts that treat volatility as sustained error requiring recalibration of precision (Clark, 2013; Raidl & Rott, 2023). The result was efficient,

contained adaptation – satisficing in function, belief-revision and predictive in mechanism – that kept D closest to the oracle benchmark derived from the true generative base rate.

Importantly, relative advantage here should be read as a fitness-indexed measure of adaptive efficiency: it captures how well an agent minimises costly utility gaps, rather than indexing epistemic accuracy alone. Converging exploratory indices reinforced this interpretation: although both C and D exhibited higher transient RMSE after shifts, only D combined lower cumulative relative advantage with reduced precision–adaptivity cost (Table 2; Fig. 3), highlighting that its adaptation was not just effective but resource-efficient over the long run.

5.1.4 H3a: Coherence stability in volatile blocks

In volatile regimes, Agent D showed more stable belief trajectories than its counterparts, reflected in higher CSI values (greater inverse-variance-weighted stability). Its update dynamics were regulated by an entropy-weighted TBI gain, a leak factor, momentum, and a hard step clamp, which together dampened unnecessary revisions while still allowing adjustments when evidence consistently favoured change. This reduced the oscillations that typically accompany rapid environmental shifts, preserving stability without neglecting true threats (Haselton & Nettle, 2006). The pattern is consistent with proposals that stability can be understood as limiting KL-misalignment between recognition and generative states (Kiefer & Hohwy, 2017) and resonates with “minimal change” strategies in belief-revision theory, where conservative updates prevent noise amplification, only yielding when signals accumulate (Vanpaemel & Navarro, 2007).

These results followed the expectation that coherence-preserving updating would yield lower representational oscillations under volatility. Exploratory indices reinforced this interpretation: D's lower KL spike counts and improved Brier calibration (Tables 2–3; Fig. 1) indicate that reduced oscillations coincided with more reliable calibration. Relatedly, decision frameworks allowing imprecise or relaxed internal states have argued that selective reductions in precision can be rational, supporting the view that coherence stability can be maintained through adaptive damping mechanisms (Fan, 2021; Smith, 2023).

5.1.5 H3b: Post-shift disruptions

Following regime shifts, both Agents C and D were associated with fewer coherence disruptions than the baselines, indicating that enriched priors buffered instability when prediction errors spiked. The difference between C and D was modest but mechanistically informative: C's affective anchoring acted like a coarse commitment to salient evidence, whereas D's TBI-modulated gain applied smoother, bounded adjustments that curbed overshoot more efficiently. This distinction parallels pooling equilibria, where affective anchoring locks into a single trajectory (C), versus hybrid equilibria, where smoother gain modulation achieves recovery through smaller, more efficient steps (D) (Huttegger & Zollman, 2012; Raidl & Rott, 2023).

This hypothesis was supported: expectations predicted an advantage for D over C, and the results provided strong evidence for this difference. However, the observed margin was modest, suggesting that affective anchoring alone was sufficient for early stabilisation, while D's bounded gain modulation contributed incremental smoothing when volatility persisted. Exploratory indices lend support to this interpretation: although both C and D showed transient error spikes after shifts, D's lower adaptivity cost (Table 2; Fig. 3) indicates that its

damping routine contained those adjustments with fewer representational reversals. Viewed together with H3a, these findings suggest that coherence stability and post-shift recovery capture complementary facets of coherence regulation – one managing stability during volatility, the other enabling efficient realignment after disruptive change.

5.2 Implications

The findings from this simulation have three main implications for Bayesian models of cognition: they extend evaluation criteria beyond accuracy, refine when priors confer benefit or cost, and demonstrate coherence as an adaptive resource. Together, these implications situate the present work within ongoing debates about ecological rationality, error management, and the value of representational stability.

A first implication is that adaptivity should be evaluated beyond accuracy alone. Ideal-observer work shows that performance depends on priors, likelihoods, and a utility function that prices outcomes via asymmetric costs; optimality is defined relative to those ecological costs and benefits, not truth alone (Geisler, 2003, 2010). Agent D's profile illustrates this teleonomic stance: resilience arose not from pointwise accuracy per se but from managing the trade-off between precision, error, and representational cost. Relative Advantage (oracle – achieved), computed against a posterior-Bayes oracle that uses the asymmetric payoff matrix, directly indexes the “utility gap” – how much payoff an agent leaves on the table. Lower values thus index adaptive efficiency, echoing Carr's (2017) view that utility gaps are opportunity costs rather than epistemic failures and Williams' (2021) view that coherence and resource limits bound rationality. This supports the broader stance that many apparent irrationalities reflect satisficing under cost asymmetries rather than accuracy-maximising ideality. Practically, it shows that utility- and stability-aware measures

(relative advantage, CSI) capture adaptivity more faithfully than accuracy alone, even when the response criterion itself is kept symmetric in the reported runs.

Secondly, in concern to when priors confer benefit or impose cost, the agent ordering ($A < B < C < D$) demonstrates that biases are adaptive only when calibrated to ecological statistics and asymmetric payoffs at evaluation (Feldman, 2013; Gigerenzer et al., 1999). Agent B's static vigilance bias often produced maladaptive false alarms when misaligned with base rates, illustrating that EMT's proposed adaptivity of asymmetric vigilance (Haselton & Nettle, 2006) depends critically on calibration. This aligns with recent work emphasising calibration boundaries (Haselton & Buss, 2000). In this respect, the present results qualify EMT's framing of vigilance as broadly adaptive, showing that when vigilance is implemented rigidly and cannot tune to ecological structure, it can reduce fitness rather than enhance it. By contrast, Agent C's affective modulation provided enhanced resilience across environmental volatility and noise, by scaling threat-consistent evidence under motivational salience. This gain-control effect mirrors optimism bias in human belief updating, where desirable information is preferentially integrated and negative news down-weighted (Sharot et al., 2011; Korn et al., 2013). Computational evidence further shows that people require less evidence to adopt desirable beliefs, a valence-dependent bias that accelerates commitment to favourable states (Gesiarz et al., 2019; Cahill & Sharot, 2016). Similarly, Bayesian models of motivated reasoning demonstrate how belief-dependent utilities reshape the effective utility landscape by making favourable states carry greater subjective value (Rigoli, 2021; Fan, 2021), clarifying why affect-weighted or coherence-preserving updates may yield increased resilience under volatility without undermining calibration.

Extending this logic, Agent D demonstrated that adaptive success also requires regulating when to update and when to conserve beliefs: its entropy-weighted TBI gain, leak factor, and bounded update size embedded fitness sensitivity and representational costs directly into learning. These mechanisms curbed unnecessary oscillations while still permitting adaptation when evidence consistently supported change. Collectively, these results indicate that vigilance-like asymmetries confer advantage only under skewed payoffs, whereas affective or coherence-sensitive priors may provide broader adaptive robustness.

A third implication is that coherence should be treated as an adaptive resource rather than a by-product of inference. Agent D's higher CSI values – reflecting reduced posterior variance when accuracy was sustained – indicate that coherence can function as a control variable in its own right. This converges with belief-revision accounts emphasising minimal-change policies, where damping and bounded updates prevent noisy reversals, and with accounts that treat imprecise representational models as rational under uncertainty, allowing selective relaxation of precision to manage volatility costs (Lee et al., 2025; Raidl & Rott, 2023). Belief-dependent utility models likewise suggest that stability itself can carry utility value, making coherence preservation self-reinforcing (Fan, 2021). The distinction between C's pooling-like anchoring and D's hybrid smoothing (Huttegger & Zollman, 2012; Vanpaemel & Navarro, 2007) illustrates how systems can trade robustness for efficiency depending on volatility. This illustrates how systems can trade robustness for efficiency depending on volatility. This implies that behavioural and computational profiles of adaptivity may diverge along pooling- versus gain-modulated regimes, with coherence regulation shaping the granularity of adjustments (Lee et al., 2025).

Ultimately, these findings suggest that cognitive adaptivity may be best understood as a joint function of ecological calibration, representational stability, and efficiency in managing error and precision. By modelling coherence as an operational construct within Bayesian inference, the present work shows how systems can preserve stability without forfeiting flexibility under uncertainty. More broadly, this may help illuminate why mental representations or beliefs take the shape they do and often display characteristic tendencies: persistence, resistance to change, and at times systematic distortion. The simulations indicate that such tendencies may not be flaws but adaptive by-products of coherence-sensitive regulation – strategies that use entropy-weighted damping and bounded updating to trade truth-like accuracy for resilience in volatile environments (Carr, 2017). In this way, the present findings do not resolve such an intricate problem concerning human cognition and its dynamics, but rather points towards an integrative framework in which representational stickiness and selective bias are better understood as evolutionarily rational responses to the costs of error, the structure of payoffs, and the need to sustain representational integrity in the face of environmental uncertainty and change (Sharot & Garrett, 2016; Varela et al., 1991) .

5.3 Generalisability

The findings provide consistent support for the prespecified hypotheses, but their generalisation is bounded by the stylised simulation framework. Most transferable are the principles revealed by the agent comparisons: enriched priors enhance adaptivity when calibrated to ecological contingencies; coherence-sensitive updating reduces costly oscillations under volatility; and cognitive performance reflects a trade-off between payoff maximisation and representational stability. These dynamics capture general features of adaptive inference under uncertainty.

By contrast, the specific modelling choices – two-alternative Gaussian categorisation, simplified priors, and heuristic coherence metrics (CSI and KL spikes) – do not map directly onto natural cognition. They provided tractable demonstrations of key mechanisms but remain abstractions that require empirical validation. Accordingly, these findings are best read as principled demonstrations under controlled assumptions rather than direct models of human cognition.

5.4 Limitations

The present findings are constrained by several methodological and theoretical factors. At the mechanistic level, the architectures used simplified change detection and fixed Bayes-risk decision rules, without state-space filters or richer adaptive policies. These simplifications enabled systematic comparisons but may have biased trade-offs, leaving open whether more flexible routines would alter the observed balance.

Secondly, another limitation concerns the operationalisation of key constructs. TBI, for instance, was reduced to a payoff matrix with entropy and resource penalties, and coherence was only directly indexed via CSI (an accuracy-weighted inverse-variance stability index) and KL spike counts. These heuristics may reveal meaningful differences between agents but compressed complex, multidimensional phenomena – epistemic, pragmatic, and affective – into tractable computational proxies that require further validation in human based research.

Furthermore, a limitation arises on Agent B's schema prior, which was implemented as a static, one-off bias rather than a per-trial schedule. This preserved consistency with runs collapses the expected U-shaped payoff curve across γT into a flat miscalibrated bias that

often underperformed the neutral baseline. Future work should implement the full γT schedule to test the richer theoretical predictions of schema-based vigilance prior that updates dynamically. A further consideration concerns the adaptive architecture of Agent D. Its updating relied on a logistic-bounded TBI gain, leak, momentum, and step clamp rather than more elaborate state-space change-point filters or multi-level coherence tracking. This implementation was sufficient to demonstrate how conservative updating routines can preserve stability under volatility, but it abstracts away from richer adaptive mechanisms that could be deployed in by cognition.

Finally, the broader framework reflects one trajectory among alternatives. The Bayesian stance assumes cognition as probabilistic updating, a view contested by dynamical, symbolic, and rule-based approaches. Likewise, the stylised taxonomy of schema, affective, and coherence-sensitive priors clarified contrasts but oversimplified their contextual overlap. Accordingly, the present study should be read as clarifying a possible path for Bayesian modelling under controlled assumptions, not a definitive map of natural cognition.

5.5 Future Directions

Future research should first pursue ecological expansion. The current Gaussian 2AFC task can be extended to multi-alternative decisions, drifting payoffs, and non-stationary hazards, with state-space filters such as Kalman or particle methods adding mechanistic realism (Lee & Wagenmakers, 2014). These extensions would test whether the observed trade-offs between enriched priors, coherence-sensitive updating, and payoff stability hold in settings closer to natural decision problems. Second, policy pluralism is needed. Beyond the fixed symmetric Bayes-risk decision rule implemented here, future work could explore

dynamic thresholds that adapt trial-by-trial to changing costs and priors, offering a closer analogue to ecological decision-making. Such thresholds could then be compared against alternative decision rules, including cost-sensitive drift-diffusion models, bounded heuristics, and satisficing policies (Gesiarz et al., 2019; Trimmer et al., 2011). Such comparisons would clarify whether coherence-sensitive updating retains its advantages across architectures and utility codings, addressing calls for pluralistic modelling frameworks in cognitive science.

Third, empirical validation remains essential. Behavioural studies, incorporating techniques such as eye-tracking, with volatility and deception manipulations could test whether CSI-like indices of representational stability replicate in human performance, while neural work could examine whether coherence-sensitive dynamics manifest in volatility signatures within prefrontal-striatal circuits or prediction-error pathways (Behrens et al., 2007; Iglesias et al., 2013). Linking behavioural and neural data would establish whether coherence stability reflects a plausible target of biological implementation rather than a computational convenience. Overall, these results highlight the value of incorporating coherence into the evaluation of cognitive models and suggest avenues for testing these ideas in richer tasks.

References

- Badcock, P. B., Friston, K. J., Ramstead, M. J. D., Ploeger, A., & Hohwy, J. (2019). The hierarchically mechanistic mind: an evolutionary systems theory of the human brain, cognition, and behavior. *Cognitive, Affective, & Behavioral Neuroscience, 19*(6), 1319–1351. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13415-019-00721-3>
- Barrett, L. F. (2016). The theory of constructed emotion: an active inference account of interoception and categorization. *Social Cognitive and Affective Neuroscience, nsw154*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scan/nsw154>
- Behrens, T. E. J., Woolrich, M. W., Walton, M. E., & Rushworth, M. F. S. (2007). Learning the value of information in an uncertain world. *Nature Neuroscience, 10*(9), 1214–1221. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nn1954>
- Bender, A. (2019). The Role of Culture and Evolution for Human Cognition. *Topics in Cognitive Science, 12*(4). <https://doi.org/10.1111/tops.12449>
- Binmore. (2007). Rational Decisions in Large Worlds. *Annales d'Économie et de Statistique, 86*, 25–41. <https://doi.org/10.2307/20079192>
- Blancke, S., & De Smedt, J. (2013). *Evolved to be irrational? Evolutionary and cognitive foundations of pseudosciences*.
- Bradie, M., & Harms, W. (2020). *Evolutionary Epistemology* (E. N. Zalta, Ed.). Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy; Metaphysics Research Lab, Stanford University. <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/epistemology-evolutionary/>
- Brighton, H., & Gigerenzer, G. (2012). Are rational actor models “rational” outside small worlds?. In S. Okasha & K. Binmore (Eds.), *Evolution and Rationality*. Cambridge University Press.
- Bruineberg, J., & Rietveld, E. (2014). Self-organization, free energy minimization, and optimal grip on a field of affordances. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience, 8*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2014.00599>

- Burnham, K. P., & Anderson, D. R. (2002). *Model Selection and Multimodel Inference: A Practical Information-Theoretic Approach*. Springer New York. <https://doi.org/10.1007/b97636>
- Campbell, D. (1974). Evolutionary Epistemology. *The Philosophy of Karl Popper, 1*, 413–459. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0140-1750\(91\)90137-f](https://doi.org/10.1016/0140-1750(91)90137-f)
- Carr, J. R. (2017). Epistemic Utility Theory and the Aim of Belief. *Philosophy and Phenomenological Research, 95*(3), 511–534. <https://doi.org/10.1111/phpr.12436>
- Clark, A. (2013). Whatever next? Predictive brains, situated agents, and the future of cognitive science. *Behavioral and Brain Sciences, 36*(3), 181–204. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0140525x12000477>
- Constant, A., Clark, A., & Friston, K. J. (2021). Representation Wars: Enacting an Armistice Through Active Inference. *Frontiers in Psychology, 11*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.598733>
- Dewey, J. (1938). *Logic : the Theory of Inquiry*. Read Books Ltd. (Original work published 1938)
- Fan, Y. (2021). A Belief-Dependent Utility Model. *Acta Mathematicae Applicatae Sinica, English Series, 37*(4), 682–696. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10255-021-1038-4>
- Feldman, J. (2013). Tuning Your Priors to the World. *Topics in Cognitive Science, 5*(1), 13–34. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tops.12003>
- Friston, K. (2010). The free-energy principle: a unified brain theory? *Nature Reviews Neuroscience, 11*(2), 127–138. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn2787>
- Friston, K. (2012). The history of the future of the Bayesian brain. *NeuroImage, 62*(2), 1230–1233. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2011.10.004>
- Friston, K. J., Rosch, R., Parr, T., Price, C., & Bowman, H. (2017). Deep temporal models and active inference. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews, 77*, 388–402. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2017.04.009>

- Friston, K., Da Costa, L., Sajid, N., Heins, C., Ueltzhöffer, K., Pavliotis, G. A., & Parr, T. (2023). The free energy principle made simpler but not too simple. *Physics Reports*, *1024*, 1–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physrep.2023.07.001>
- Friston, K., Fortier, M., & Friedman, D. (2018). Of woodlice and men A Bayesian account of cognition, life and consciousness. An interview with Karl Friston [Interview]. In *ALIUS Bulletin*. ALIUS Bulletin.
- Friston, K., Kilner, J., & Harrison, L. (2006). A free energy principle for the brain. *Journal of Physiology-Paris*, *100*(1-3), 70–87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jphysparis.2006.10.001>
- Friston, K., Rigoli, F., Ognibene, D., Mathys, C., Fitzgerald, T., & Pezzulo, G. (2015). Active inference and epistemic value. *Cognitive Neuroscience*, *6*(4), 187–214. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17588928.2015.1020053>
- Geisler, W. (2003). A Bayesian approach to the evolution of perceptual and cognitive systems. *Cognitive Science*, *27*(3), 379–402. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0364-0213\(03\)00009-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0364-0213(03)00009-0)
- Geisler, W. S. (2008). Visual Perception and the Statistical Properties of Natural Scenes. *Annual Review of Psychology*, *59*, 167–192. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.58.110405.085632>
- Genewein, T., Leibfried, F., Grau-Moya, J., & Braun, D. A. (2015). Bounded Rationality, Abstraction, and Hierarchical Decision-Making: An Information-Theoretic Optimality Principle. *Frontiers in Robotics and AI*, *2*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frobt.2015.00027>
- Gesiarz, F., Cahill, D., & Sharot, T. (2019). Evidence accumulation is biased by motivation: A computational account. *PLOS Computational Biology*, *15*(6), e1007089. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1007089>
- Gigerenzer, G. (2002). Bounded rationality: The adaptive toolbox. *Psychology and Marketing*, *20*(1), 87–92. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mar.10060>

- Gigerenzer, G. (2008). Why Heuristics Work. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 3(1), 20–29.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-6916.2008.00058.x>
- Gigerenzer, G., & Gaissmaier, W. (2011). Heuristic Decision Making. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 62(1), 451–482. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-120709-145346>
- Gładziejewski, P. (2015). Predictive coding and representationalism. *Synthese*, 193(2), 559–582.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11229-015-0762-9>
- Godfrey-Smith, P. (1996). Précis of Complexity and the Function of Mind in Nature. *Adaptive Behavior*, 4(3-4), 453–465. <https://doi.org/10.1177/105971239600400308>
- Hammerstein, P. (2012). Towards a Darwinian theory of decision making: games and the biological roots of behavior . In S. Okasha & K. Binmore (Eds.), *Evolution and Rationality Decisions, Co-operation and Strategic Behaviour” Excerpt*. Cambridge University Press.
- Haselton, M. G., Bryant, G. A., Wilke, A., Frederick, D. A., Galperin, A., Frankenhuys, W. E., & Moore, T. (2009). Adaptive Rationality: An Evolutionary Perspective on Cognitive Bias. *Social Cognition*, 27(5), 733–763. <https://doi.org/10.1521/soco.2009.27.5.733>
- Haselton, M. G., & Buss, D. M. (2000). Error management theory: A new perspective on biases in cross-sex mind reading. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 78(1), 81–91.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.78.1.81>
- Haselton, M. G., & Nettle, D. (2006). The Paranoid Optimist: An Integrative Evolutionary Model of Cognitive Biases. *Personality and Social Psychology Review*, 10(1), 47–66.
https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327957pspr1001_3
- Hoffman, D. D., Singh, M., & Prakash, C. (2015). The Interface Theory of Perception. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*, 22(6), 1480–1506. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13423-015-0890-8>
- Huttegger, S., & Zollman, K. (2012). Evolution, dynamics and rationality: The limits of ESS methodology. In S. Okasha & K. Binmore (Eds.), *Evolution and Rationality: Decisions, Co-operation and Strategic Behaviour*. Cambridge University Press.

- Iglesias, S., Mathys, C., Brodersen, Kay H., Kasper, L., Piccirelli, M., den Ouden, Hanneke E. M., & Stephan, Klaas E. (2013). Hierarchical Prediction Errors in Midbrain and Basal Forebrain during Sensory Learning. *Neuron*, *80*(2), 519–530.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2013.09.009>
- Jakob Hohwy. (2013). *The predictive mind*. Oxford University Press.
- James, W. (1907). *Pragmatism: A new name for some old ways of thinking*. Longmans, Green and Co. <https://doi.org/10.1037/10851-000>
- Kiefer, A., & Hohwy, J. (2017). Content and misrepresentation in hierarchical generative models. *Synthese*, *195*(6), 2387–2415. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11229-017-1435-7>
- Knill, D. C., & Pouget, A. (2004). The Bayesian brain: the role of uncertainty in neural coding and computation. *Trends in Neurosciences*, *27*(12), 712–719.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tins.2004.10.007>
- Lee, H., Lim, J., & Lee, S.-H. (2025). Belief updating in decision-variable space: past decisions with finer granularity attract future ones more strongly. *IScience*, *28*(7), 112844–112844.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2025.112844>
- Lee, M. D., & Eric-Jan Wagenmakers. (2014). *Bayesian Cognitive Modeling*. Cambridge University Press.
- Legg, C., & Hookway, C. (2008, August 16). *Pragmatism*. Stanford.edu; The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Winter 2024 Edition).
<https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/win2024/entries/pragmatism/>
- Lo, A., & Zhang, R. (2021). The evolutionary origin of Bayesian heuristics and finite memory. *IScience*, *24*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci>
- Millikan, R. G. (1989). Biosemantics. *The Journal of Philosophy*, *86*(6), 281.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/2027123>

- Mollo, D. C. (2019). Are There Teleological Functions to Compute? *Philosophy of Science*, 86(3), 431–452. <https://doi.org/10.1086/703554>
- Murphy, P. (2006). Coherentism. In *Internet Encyclopedia of Philosophy*.
<https://iep.utm.edu/coherentism-in-epistemology/#:~:text=Coherentism%20is%20a%20theory%20of,these%20relations%20in%20different%20ways>.
- Pezzulo, G., Rigoli, F., & Friston, K. J. (2018). Hierarchical Active Inference: A Theory of Motivated Control. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 22(4), 294–306.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2018.01.009>
- Prakash, C., Stephens, K. D., Hoffman, D. D., Singh, M., & Fields, C. (2021). Fitness Beats Truth in the Evolution of Perception. *Acta Biotheoretica*, 69(3), 319–341.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10441-020-09400-0>
- Quine, W. V. (1980). *From a logical point of view*. Harvard University Press.
- Raidl, E., & Rott, H. (2023). Threshold-Based Belief Change Australasian Journal of Logic
Threshold-based belief change: Rankings and semiorders. *Article in the Australasian Journal of Logic*. <https://doi.org/10.26686/ajl.v20i3.7408>
- Ramstead, M. J. D., Veissière, S. P. L., & Kirmayer, L. J. (2016). Cultural Affordances: Scaffolding Local Worlds Through Shared Intentionality and Regimes of Attention. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2016.01090>
- Rescorla, M. (2024). *Bayesian Models of the Mind*. Cambridge University Press.
- Rigoli, F., Martinelli, C., & Pezzulo, G. (2021). I want to believe: delusion, motivated reasoning, and Bayesian decision theory. *Cognitive Neuropsychiatry*, 26(6), 408–420.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13546805.2021.1982686>
- Sharot, T., & Garrett, N. (2016). Special Focus on Emotion Forming Beliefs: Why Valence Matters. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 20(1). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2015.11.002>

- Shea, N. (2023). Organized representations forming a computationally useful processing structure. *Synthese*, 202(6). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11229-023-04373-2>
- Smith, N. (2023). Acting on belief functions. *Theory and Decision*, 95, 575–621. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11238-023-09937-9>
- Stankevicius, A., Huys, Q. J. M., Kalra, A., & Seriès, P. (2014). Optimism as a Prior Belief about the Probability of Future Reward. *PLoS Computational Biology*, 10(5), e1003605. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1003605>
- Sterelny, K. (2012). From fitness to utility. In S. Okasha & K. Binmore (Eds.), *Evolution and Rationality*. Cambridge University Press.
- Tenenbaum, J. B., Kemp, C., Griffiths, T. L., & Goodman, N. D. (2011). How to Grow a Mind: Statistics, Structure, and Abstraction. *Science*, 331(6022), 1279–1285. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1192788>
- Tomasello, M. (2014). *A Natural History of Human Thinking*. <https://doi.org/10.4159/9780674726369>
- Trimmer, P. C., Houston, A. I., Marshall, J. A. R., Mendl, M. T., Paul, E. S., & McNamara, J. M. (2011). Decision-making under uncertainty: biases and Bayesians. *Animal Cognition*, 14(4), 465–476. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10071-011-0387-4>
- Ültanır, E. (2012). An Epistemological Glance At The Constructivist Approach: Constructivist Learning In Dewey, Piaget, And Montessori. *International Journal of Instruction*, 5(2), 195–212. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED533786.pdf>
- Vanpaemel, W., & Navarro, D. (2007). *Representational Shifts During Category Learning* (pp. 1599–1604).
- Varela, F. J., Rosch, E., & Thompson, E. (1991). *The Embodied Mind*. MIT Press. https://monoskop.org/images/2/21/Varela_Thompson_Rosch_The_Embodied_Mind_Cognitive_Science_and_Human_Experience_1991.pdf

- Verendeev, A., & Sherwood, C. C. (2017). Human brain evolution. *Current Opinion in Behavioral Sciences*, 16, 41–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cobeha.2017.02.003>
- Wacongne, C., Labyt, E., van Wassenhove, V., Bekinschtein, T., Naccache, L., & Dehaene, S. (2011). Evidence for a hierarchy of predictions and prediction errors in human cortex. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 108(51), 20754–20759. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1117807108>
- Wicks, R. (2017). *Arthur Schopenhauer* (*Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*). Stanford.edu. <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/schopenhauer/>
- Wiese, W. (2016). What are the contents of representations in predictive processing? *Phenomenology and the Cognitive Sciences*, 16(4), 715–736. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11097-016-9472-0>
- Williams, D. (2017). Predictive Processing and the Representation Wars. *Minds and Machines*, 28(1), 141–172. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11023-017-9441-6>
- Williams, D. (2021). Epistemic irrationality in the Bayesian brain . *The British Journal for the Philosophy of Science*, 72(4), 913–938. <https://doi.org/10.1093/BJPS/AXZ044>
- Williams, D. F. (2018). Pragmatism and the predictive mind. *Phenomenology and the Cognitive Sciences*, 17(5), 835–859. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11097-017-9556-5>
- Wolff, J. G. (2019). Information Compression as a Unifying Principle in Human Learning, Perception, and Cognition. *Complexity*, 2019, 1–38. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/1879746>
- Yon, D., Heyes, C., & Press, C. (2020). Beliefs and desires in the predictive brain. *Nature Communications*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-18332-9>
- Young, J. O. (2018, June 26). *The Coherence Theory of Truth*. Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy. <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/truth-coherence/>

Appendix A

Global Descriptives and Baseline Performance

Table A1.

Mean (\pm 95% CI) performance metrics across agents (averaged over 50 seeds)

Agent	Fitness (mean \pm 95%CI)	Relative Adv (mean \pm 95%CI)	CSI (mean \pm 95%CI)	KL spikes (mean \pm 95%CI)
A	1084.08 \pm 12.05	185.33 \pm 7.44	1.12 \pm 0.02	704.12 \pm 4.25
B	1043.76 \pm 12.56	225.65 \pm 7.5	1.13 \pm 0.02	695.58 \pm 4.49
C	1272.44 \pm 11.05	-3.04 \pm 5.18	1.83 \pm 0.08	573.44 \pm 5.7
D	1288.71 \pm 11.12	-19.31 \pm 4.53	2.76 \pm 0.35	563.5 \pm 6.76

Note. Values represent means \pm 95% confidence intervals across 50 random seeds. CSI = Coherence Stability Index; KL = Kullback–Leibler divergence spike count.

Figure A1

Global performance metrics across agents

Note. Bar plots show cumulative values aggregated across all 1,000 trials (totals summed across the run and averaged over 50 seeds). Fitness payoff = total payoff accumulated across trials; KL spikes = total count of divergence spikes; CSI = Coherence Stability Index; $\Sigma\Delta\pi$ = Precision–adaptivity cost; RMSE = Root Mean Square Error.

Table A2*Per-trial mean payoff across regimes (mean \pm 95% CI)*

Regime	Agent A	Agent B	Agent C	Agent D
Stable	2.06 \pm 0.06	1.93 \pm 0.06	2.15 \pm 0.07	2.18 \pm 0.06
Volatile	1.75 \pm 0.02	1.70 \pm 0.02	2.09 \pm 0.01	2.12 \pm 0.01
Deceptive	0.01 \pm 0.06	0.03 \pm 0.06	0.21 \pm 0.07	0.26 \pm 0.06

Note. Values represent mean per-trial payoff (\pm 95% CI, half-width) averaged across 50 seeds. Reporting on a per-trial basis normalises for unequal regime lengths (stable = 100, volatile = 500, deceptive = 50), allowing direct cross-regime comparison.

Table A3*Per-trial Relative Advantage (\pm 95% CI)*

Regime	Agent A	Agent B	Agent C	Agent D
Stable	-0.00 \pm 0.00	0.12 \pm 0.02	-0.09 \pm 0.04	-0.12 \pm 0.02
Volatile	0.37 \pm 0.02	0.43 \pm 0.02	0.03 \pm 0.01	0.01 \pm 0.01
Deceptive	0.00 \pm 0.00	-0.02 \pm 0.03	-0.20 \pm 0.05	-0.25 \pm 0.03

Note. Values represent mean per-trial relative advantage (oracle – achieved; \pm 95% CI, half-width) averaged across 50 seeds. Lower values indicate better performance, with negative values reflecting stochastic surpassing of the oracle. Per-trial reporting normalises for unequal regime lengths, allowing direct cross-regime comparison.

Figure A2.

Descriptive plots for H1 (Fitness Payoff).

Note. Panels show payoff contrasts A-B (left), A-C (middle), and A-D (right). Values represent mean cumulative fitness payoff across 1,000 trials ($N = 50$ seeds per agent). Error bars indicate 95% confidence intervals. Higher values reflect greater total reward obtained across the full task.

Figure A3

Bayes Factor robustness checks for H1 (Fitness Payoff).

Note. Panels show robustness across prior widths for payoff contrasts. For A-C (middle) and A-D (right), Bayes factors remain decisively in favour of H_1 across prior widths; for A-B (left), evidence is decisive at the default prior but becomes weaker/ambiguous under very wide priors.

Figure A4

Seed-wise paired differences for H1 (Fitness Payoff).

Note. Panels show histograms with normal density overlays (left) and Q-Q plots (right) for payoff contrasts A-B (top), A-C (middle), and A-D (bottom). Distributions reflect per-seed cumulative payoff differences ($N = 50$). Q-Q plots indicate approximate normality for A-B and A-C, with mild deviations visible for A-D in the tails.

Figure A5

Descriptive plots for H2 (Relative Advantage).

Note. Panels show relative advantage of contrasts D-A (left), D-B (middle), and D-C (right).

Values represent mean cumulative relative advantage across 1,000 trials ($N = 50$ seeds per agent). Lower values indicate better performance (agents surpassing oracle baseline). Error bars indicate 95% confidence intervals.

Figure A6

Bayes Factor robustness checks for H2 (Relative Advantage).

Note. Panels show robustness across prior widths for contrasts D-A (left), D-B (middle), and D-C (right). Bayes factors remain decisively in favour of H_1 across all prior widths for D-A and D-B; for D-C, evidence supports H_1 but at a reduced magnitude relative to the other contrasts.

Figure A7

Seed-wise paired differences for H2 (Relative Advantage).

Note. Panels show histograms with normal density overlays (left) and Q-Q plots (right) for contrasts A-B (top), A-C (middle), and A-D (bottom). Distributions reflect per-seed cumulative relative advantage differences ($N = 50$). Q-Q plots indicate approximate normality across contrasts, with mild departures visible in the tails for A-B and A-D.

Figure A8

Descriptive plots for H3a (Coherence Stability Index).

Note. Panels show mean CSI with 95% confidence intervals for contrasts D–A (left), D–B (middle), and D–C (right). Values represent mean volatile-block CSI across 1,000 trials ($N = 50$ seeds per agent). Higher CSI values indicate greater coherence stability; error bars reflect 95% CIs.

Figure A9

Bayes Factor robustness checks for H3a (Coherence Stability Index).

Note. Panels show robustness checks across prior widths for contrasts D–A (left), D–B (middle), and D–C (right). Bayes factors remained in favor of H_1 for D–A and D–B across all prior widths, while evidence for D–C was weaker relative to the other contrasts.

Figure A10

Seed-wise paired differences for H3a (Coherence Stability Index).

Note. Panels show histograms with normal density overlays (left) and Q-Q plots (right) for contrasts A-B (top), A-C (middle), and A-D (bottom). Distributions reflect per-seed volatile-block CSI differences ($N = 50$). Q-Q plots indicate approximate normality overall, with mild lower-tail skew for A-C and A-D.

Figure A11

Descriptive plots for H3b (Coherence Disruptions; KL spike counts).

Note. Panels show mean cumulative KL spike counts ($\pm 95\%$ CI) for contrasts D–A (left), D–B (middle), and D–C (right). Values reflect global KL spike counts aggregated across 1,000 trials ($N = 50$ seeds per agent). Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals. Higher counts indicate greater coherence disruptions; lower values reflect more stable coherence.

Figure A12

Bayes Factor robustness checks for H3b (Coherence Disruptions; KL spike counts).

Note. Panels show Bayes factor robustness checks across Cauchy prior widths for contrasts D–A (left), D–B (middle), and D–C (right). Bayes factors provided decisive evidence for D < A and D < B across all prior widths. For D–C, Bayes factors remained large but were smaller and more prior-sensitive, yielding strong but less robust evidence for D < C.

Figure A13

Seed-wise paired differences for H3b (Coherence Disruptions; KL spike counts).

Note. Panels show histograms with normal density overlays (left) and Q-Q plots (right) for contrasts A-B (top), A-C (middle), and A-D (bottom). Distributions reflect per-seed global KL spike count differences ($N = 50$). Q-Q plots suggest approximate normality for A-B and A-C, with mild positive skew visible for A-D.

Appendix B

Formal Specification of the Simulation Model

This appendix provides the formal specification of the simulation model as implemented in the code. Section B.1 lists all symbols and parameters with definitions and constants. Section B.2 presents the core simulation equations. Section B.3 details the agent-specific update rules (A–D), and Section B.4 defines the performance metrics (epistemic fit, utility, coherence stability, and adaptive efficiency).

B.1 Symbols and Parameters

Table B1.1

Core Symbols and Parameters

Symbol	Definition / Use	Default / Constants
x_t	Stimulus at trial t , drawn from Gaussian generative model.	$\mu_T = +1.25$, $\mu_N = -1.25$, $\sigma^2 = 1$
y_t	True category label (“Threat” or “Non-threat”).	–
π_t	Prior belief weight on “Threat” at trial t .	Initialisation varies by agent (A–D).
$p_t(T x_t)$	Posterior probability of “Threat” given stimulus.	Computed via Bayes rule
τ_t	Decision threshold. Fixed in all runs as 0.5.	Fixed in all runs for agents as 0.5
U	Fitness payoff from payoff matrix.	{+2, –2, +0.25, –0.25} for {hit, miss, correct-rej, false-alarm}.
h	Hazard rate governing volatility (probability of regime switch each trial).	$1/80 \approx 0.0125$.
Δ	Signal discriminability (half the separation between class means).	1.25.
p	Base-rate disparity, controls probability of Threat vs Non-threat.	$p_H = 0.9$, $p_L = 0.1$ in probe runs.

Symbol	Definition / Use	Default / Constants
β	Fitness scaling weight (applies ecological payoffs in TBI cost).	$\beta = 2.0$.
δ	Entropy/precision penalty weight	$\delta = 0.1$.
T	Total number of trials per run.	1000
S	Number of seeds (independent replicates per condition).	50

Table B1.2*Agent-Specific Parameters*

Agent	Symbol	Definition / Role	Defaults / Constants
Agent A	$\pi_0(T)$	Initial prior probability of “Threat.”	0.5 (uniform).
	τ	Decision threshold.	Fixed at 0.5 (symmetric).
	γ_T	Prior exponent applied to Threat at $t=1$.	Varied (configurable); $\gamma_N = 1$.
Agent B	$\widetilde{\pi}_T$	Exponentiated threat prior.	-
	$\pi_1(T)$	Initialised threat prior after exponentiation.	Clipped to [0.05, 0.95].
	$\pi_t(T)$	Threat prior after $t=1$.	Held constant across trials
	τ	Decision threshold.	Fixed at 0.5.

Agent	Symbol	Definition / Role	Defaults / Constants
Agent C	v_t^{val}	Valence term (20-trial window proportion of threats).	0.73 if mean proportion > 0.5; else 0.20.
	s_t	Surprise signal, non-linear response to posterior vs. perceived label discrepancy.	Exponent 1.5 applied.
	g_t	Affective gain with exponential decay.	Decay factor $r \approx 0.95$.
	target_t	Target prior value.	Offset $b_0 = 0.5$; gain γ configurable.
	$\pi_{t+1}(T)$	Updated threat prior.	Clipped to [0.05, 0.95]; leak rate $l \in (0, 1)$.
	τ	Decision threshold.	Fixed at 0.5.
Agent D	α_t^{eff}	Effective learning rate	$\alpha_{\text{base}} = 0.05$, $\lambda_t = \text{logistic}(\text{TBI_score}; \text{k_map} = 2)$
	λ_t^{TBI}	Multiplicative gain from TBI score (utility $\beta - \text{entropy } \delta$). Logistic-bounded in $[\lambda_{\text{min}}, \lambda_{\text{max}}]$.	$\lambda_{\text{min}} = 0.35$ $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 0.85$
	κ_t	Leak/damping factor	Range [0.50, 0.95].
	momentum_t	Momentum term, carries sign of updates.	Capped ≤ 0.12 .
	step_t	Bounded update step.	Clamped to $\pm \text{max_step}$ (default 0.25)
	$\pi_{t+1}(T)$	Updated threat prior.	Clipped to [0.02, 0.98].
	τ	Decision threshold.	Fixed at 0.5

Table B1.3*Metrics Symbols and Defaults*

Symbol	Definition / Use	Default / Constant
w	Window length for CSI moving variance (on posteriors).	50 trials (movvar, endpoints shrunk)
v_t^{CSI}	Local posterior variance (windowed) used in CSI.	Floored at 10^{-3} before normalisation
v_{\min}	CSI local variance floor before normalisation	10^{-3}
\bar{v}	Global variance normaliser for CSI.	$\bar{v} = \max(\text{var}(\pi_{1:T}), 10^{-3})$
a_t	Exponentially smoothed accuracy trace for CSI.	Smoothing $\delta = 0.1$
δ^{EMA}	EMA smoothing constant used in a_t	0.60
ϵ	CSI denominator floor (numerical stabiliser).	10^{-6}
CSI_t	Coherence Stability Index (per-trial; averaged per block for reporting).	Uses $w, \delta^{\text{EMA}}, \epsilon, \bar{v}$ as above
D_{KL}	KL divergence used for ‘‘KL spikes’’.	Forward order in code: $D_{\text{KL}}(\pi_{t-1} \pi_t)$; natural log
τ_{KL}	KL-spike threshold.	0.05 (nats)
$\pi_t(T)$	Posterior probability of ‘‘Threat’’ at trial t .	Clipped to $[0.05, 0.95]$ upstream; no extra eps in metrics
\hat{y}_t, y_t	Predicted label; true label (for accuracy/Brier/RMSE).	Binary {Threat, Non-threat}
$\Sigma\Delta\pi$	Precision-adaptivity cost (stability-flexibility metric).	–
T	Trials per run (for metric normalisation).	1000
Blocks	Regime partitions for per-block summaries.	Stable 100, Volatile 500, Deceptive 50

B.2 Core Task Equations

B.2.1 Generative task

Stimuli were generated from Gaussian distributions:

$$x_t \sim \begin{cases} \mathcal{N}(\mu_T, \sigma^2), & Y_t = \text{Threat} \\ \mathcal{N}(\mu_N, \sigma^2), & Y_t = \text{Non - threat}, \end{cases}$$

with parameters $\mu_T = +1.25$, $\mu_N = -1.25$, and $\sigma^2 = 1$.

Signal discriminability Δ :

$$\Delta = \frac{\mu_T - \mu_N}{2}, \quad d' = \frac{2\Delta}{\sigma}.$$

B.2.2 Bayesian posterior (common to all agents)

$$p_t(T | x_1) = \frac{p(x_t | T) \pi_{t-1}(T)}{\sum_{y \in \{T, N\}} p(x_t | y) \pi_{t-1}(y)}.$$

B.3 Decision Rule

Utilities were defined as $\{+2, -2, +0.25, -0.25\}$

for {hit, miss, correct rejection, false alarm}, implying costs:

$$C_{FN} = 2, \quad C_{FP} = 0.25.$$

The Bayes-risk rule prescribes choosing ‘‘Threat’’ whenever:

$$p_t(T | x_t) \geq \tau_t, \quad \tau_t = \frac{C_{FP}}{C_{FN} + C_{FP}} \approx 0.111.$$

In the reported runs, all agents (A–D) instead used a fixed symmetric threshold:

$\tau = 0.5$, to ensure comparability. The asymmetric τ was retained only for payoff expectations.

B.4 Agent-Specific Priors and Updates

B.4.1 Agent A (flat-prior baseline)

$$\pi_0(T) = 0.5,$$

With beliefs updated by Eq. (B.2.2) and decision by Eq. (B.3) with $\tau = 0.5$.

B.4.2 Agent B (static vigilance prior; one-off exponentiation)

At $t = 1$, the threat prior was initialised at the neutral value $\pi_T = 0.5$ and sharpened through exponentiation:

$$\widetilde{\pi}_T = \frac{\pi_T^{\gamma_T}}{\pi_T^{\gamma_T} + (1 - \pi_T)^{\gamma_N}}, \quad \gamma_N = 1,$$

with $\pi_T = 0.5$ as the neutral starting prior.

This was then clipped for stability to the interval $[0.05, 0.95]$,

$$\pi_1(T) = \text{clip}[0.05, 0.95](\widetilde{\pi}_T)$$

and held constant for all subsequent trials:

$$\pi_t(T) \equiv \pi_1(T) \quad \forall t \geq 1$$

The decision rule used a symmetric threshold, $\tau = 0.5$.

B.4.3 Agent C (affect-modulated prior)

Agent C began with a neutral prior ($\pi_1 = 0.5$) and updated it through a bounded leak mechanism modulated by valence and surprise.

1. Valence term (windowed evidence):

$$v_t^{\text{val}} = \begin{cases} 0.73, & \text{if } \text{mean}(\text{perc}_{t-19:t}) > 0.5 \\ 0.20, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where $\text{perc}_{t-19:t}$ is the proportion of threat stimuli over the past 20 trials.

2. Affective surprise signal:

$$s_t = \tanh(|\pi_t - \text{perc}_t|^{1.5}),$$

capturing deviations between the current prior (π_t) and the perceived category (perc_t).

3. Target prior:

$$\text{target}_t = v_t + b_0 + \gamma s_t, \quad b_0 \approx 0.5,$$

where b_0 is a bias constant and γ a gain parameter

4. Leaky update:

$$\pi_{t+1} = \lambda \pi_t + (1 - \lambda) \text{target}_t,$$

with $\lambda \approx 0.95$. Values were clipped to $[0.05, 0.95]$ for stability.

The decision threshold was fixed at $\tau = 0.5$.

B.4.4 Agent D (TBI gain with leak, momentum, and clamp)

Agent D implemented a Teleonomic Bayesian (TBI) update designed to balance stability with flexibility. On each trial, a TBI score combining expected utility (weighted by β) and an entropy penalty (weighted by δ) was mapped through a logistic into a bounded gain $\lambda_{tbi} \in [0.35, 0.85]$, which scaled the base learning rate:

$$\alpha_t^{\text{eff}} = \lambda_{tbi} \cdot \alpha_{\text{base}}$$

The raw update drive toward the posterior was leak-damped ($\kappa_t \in [0.2, 0.98]$) and shaped by a soft momentum term (capped ≤ 0.12) that propagated consistent update directions. A hard step clamp ($\pm \text{max_step}$, default 0.25) limited abrupt changes. Priors were updated as:

$$\pi_{t+1}(T) = \text{clip}[\pi_{\min}, \pi_{\max}](\pi_t(T) + \text{step}_t).$$

Decisions used the same fixed symmetric threshold ($\tau = 0.5$) as all other agents; the Bayes-risk threshold τ_t was retained only for oracle benchmarks. Together, the entropy-weighted TBI gain, leak/momentum, and step clamp provided a coherence-preserving update: conservative when evidence was ambiguous, but responsive when fitness-weighted discrepancies accumulate.

B.5 Metrics

All performance measures were computed per run using the logged posterior probabilities, responses, and utilities.

B.5.1 Epistemic fit – measured inference fidelity.

B.5.1.2 Accuracy: the proportion of correct classifications.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T 1\{\hat{y}_t = y_t\},$$

B.5.1.3 Area under the ROC curve (AUC): indexes overall discriminative ability across thresholds

The AUC was computed by varying the decision threshold across $[0,1]$, plotting the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) from true positive vs. false positive rates, and calculating the enclosed area.

B.5.1.4 Brier score: measures the mean squared error of probabilistic predictions.

$$\text{Brier} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T (\pi_t(T) - 1\{y_t = T\})^2.$$

B.5.1.5 Root mean square error (RMSE): was computed against the oracle posterior (posterior–Bayes target).

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T (\pi_t(T) - 1\{y_t = T\})^2},$$

This was applied globally. A transient RMSE variant was also computed over ± 15 -trial windows around regime shifts.

B.5.2 Instrumental utility – captured ecological success.

B.5.2.1 Fitness payoff: the cumulative utility from the asymmetric payoff matrix

$\{+2, -2, +0.25, -0.25\}$.

$$U = \sum_{t=1}^T u_t,$$

B.5.2.2 Relative advantage (variable name regret in code)

$$\text{Advantage} = \sum_{t=1}^T (U_t^{\text{oracle}} - U_t^{\text{realised}}),$$

where U_t^{oracle} was the payoff from an oracle that used the true base rate to form the posterior and applied the same symmetric threshold ($\tau = 0.5$) as all agents. Lower values indicate greater efficiency; negative values occur when realised payoff exceeds the oracle due to stochasticity.

B.5.3 Coherence stability - measured representational stability.

B.5.3.1 Coherence Stability Index (CSI)

On each trial we compute:

$$v_t^{\text{CSI}} = \text{movvar}(\pi_{t-w+1:t}) \quad (\text{endpoints shrunk}),$$

the local moving variance of posterior threat probabilities over a window of length w .

$$\bar{v} = \max(\text{var}(\pi_{1:T}), 10^{-3}), \quad v_t \leftarrow \max(v_t, 10^{-3}) / \bar{v},$$

where \bar{v} normalises variance by the global variance across the run, floored at 10^{-3} for stability; the local variance v_t is also floored at 10^{-3} .

$$a_t = \delta 1\{\hat{y}_t = y_t\} + (1 - \delta) a_{t-1},$$

an exponentially smoothed accuracy trace with smoothing constant $\delta^{\text{EMA}} = 0.60$

$$\text{CSI}_t = \frac{a_t}{v_t + \varepsilon}, \quad \varepsilon = 10^{-6}.$$

The CSI at each trial is the ratio of smoothed accuracy to (normalised, floored) posterior variance. Reported CSI is the block mean of CSI_t

B.5.3.2 Kullback-Liebler (KL) spikes

KL spikes. For each trial $t > 1$ we compute the forward Kullback–Leibler divergence (in nats) from the posterior at $t - 1$ to the posterior at t :

$$D_{\text{KL}}(\pi_{t-1} | \pi_t) = \pi_{t-1} \log \frac{\pi_{t-1}}{\pi_t} + (1 - \pi_{t-1}) \log \frac{1 - \pi_{t-1}}{1 - \pi_t}.$$

Probabilities were clipped to $[10^{-6}, 1 - 10^{-6}]$ to avoid undefined logs.

A “KL spike” was registered when $D_{\text{KL}}(\pi_t | \pi_{t-1}) > \tau_{\text{KL}}$, with $\tau_{\text{KL}} = 0.05$.

Robustness to threshold choice is reported in Appendix C (Table C5; Figure C5).

B.5.4 Adaptive efficiency – measured stability-flexibility trade-offs.

B.5.4.1 Precision-adaptivity cost ($\Sigma|\Delta\pi|$) was the cumulative absolute change in the prior probability of threat π across trials.

$$\Sigma\Delta\pi = \sum_{t=1}^T |\pi_t - \pi_{t-1}|,$$

B.5.4.2 RMSE (transitions)

Transient RMSE (as per B.5.1.5) also indexes adaptive error cost following regime shifts.

B.5.5 Code Availability

The exact simulation code used in this dissertation is openly archived on Zenodo and linked to a GitHub repository. The archive includes all core scripts (run_repro.m, config_bayesian_categorisation.m, restoreOGSchedule.m, generateStimuli.m, initAgents.m, simulateAgents.m, agent_logic.m, computeMetrics.m, and seedList.m) required to reproduce the analyses. The preserved version ensures full reproducibility of results and provides a persistent DOI for citation: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17173916>

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Appendix C

Sensitivity, Robustness, and Ablation Analyses

This appendix presents supplementary analyses assessing the robustness of agent performance. Results include one-way and two-way interactions parameter sweeps, Latin hypercube Sampling (LHS) sensitivity tests, edge-case stress tests, and ablation experiments. Together, these analyses provide additional context for the main findings reported in the Results section.

Figure C1

Kullback–Leibler Divergence Peaks per Environmental Change Across Agents A–D

Note. Boxplots show the distribution of maximum KL divergence values following environmental change points across agents (A–D) and seeds.

Figure C2.

Kullback-Leibler Area Under the Curve (AUC) per Environmental Change Across Agents A-D

Note. Boxplots show the distribution of integrated KL divergence (area under the curve) following environmental change points across agents (A–D) and seeds.

Figure C3.

Relative Performance of Agent D Compared with Baseline Agents Across β on Payoff, CSI, and KL Spikes.

Note. Lines show mean differences with 95% CIs (shaded). Positive values indicate higher scores for Agent D.

Table C1.

One-Way β Grid Analysis for Agent D Across Fitness, Relative Advantage, CSI, and KL

Spikes

β	Fitness	Relative Advantage	CSI	KL Spikes
0	882.54	94.06	1.87	603.86
0.5	907.15	69.45	2.01	595.30
1	928.15	48.45	2.07	590.60
2	945.32	31.28	2.08	591.18
3	948.14	28.46	2.06	591.98

Note. Values are means across seeds for Agent D at $\beta = 0, 0.5, 1, 2, 3$

Figure C4

Agent D Performance Across $\beta \times$ Hazard Interaction analyses.

Note. Mean values across 50 seeds are shown for fitness payoff, relative advantage, coherence stability index (CSI), and KL spike counts. Lines represent mean trajectories across β values (0, 1, 2, 3) for each hazard level ($h = 0, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2$).

Table C2*Agent D Performance Across $\beta \times$ Hazard Conditions.*

Hazard (h)	β	Fitness	Relative Advantage	CSI	KL Spikes
0.00	0	937.41	1.03	1.664	435.62
	1	946.12	-7.67	1.683	425.88
	2	958.59	-20.14	1.541	463.68
	3	962.14	-23.70	1.496	478.52
0.05	0	874.47	114.24	1.128	659.66
	1	930.10	58.61	1.165	649.04
	2	941.67	47.03	1.167	648.10
	3	942.62	46.08	1.166	648.44
0.10	0	878.61	118.59	0.979	683.38
	1	936.43	60.77	0.986	672.98
	2	943.82	53.38	0.986	671.50
	3	944.42	52.78	0.986	671.92
0.20	0	881.23	119.98	0.917	710.20
	1	939.87	61.34	0.915	702.80
	2	947.68	53.52	0.914	701.22
	3	947.17	54.03	0.914	701.54

Note. Values are means across 50 seeds. Metrics include fitness payoff, relative advantage, coherence stability index (CSI), and KL spike count. Hazard conditions are shown for $h = (0, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2)$ across $\beta = (0, 1, 2, 3.)$

Table C3

One-Way Hazard Grid Analysis for Agent D Across Fitness, Relative Advantage, CSI, and KL Spikes

Hazard	Fitness	Relative Advantage	CSI	KL Spikes
0.00	958.59	-20.14	1.54	463.68
0.05	941.67	47.03	1.17	648.10
0.10	943.82	53.38	0.99	671.50
0.20	947.68	53.52	0.91	701.22

Note. Hazard applies only within the volatile block; the schedule still includes block transitions and a deceptive segment at all h, so KL spikes remain nonzero at h=0. Values are averaged over 50 seeds at $\beta = 2.0$.

Table C4*KL Spike Threshold Sensitivity Sweep for Agent D*

τKL (threshold)	Spike Count ($\times 10^4$)
0.02	3.28
0.03	3.08
0.04	2.92
0.05	2.82
0.06	2.72
0.07	2.63
0.08	2.56
0.09	2.51
0.10	2.46

Note. Values represent mean spike counts across thresholds, based on one seed ($n = 1$).

Counts are expressed in units of $\times 10^4$. No variability estimates are shown.

Figure C5*KL Spike Sensitivity to Threshold for Agent D*

Note. Mean spike counts are plotted across τ_{KL} values from 0.02 to 0.10. Vertical dashed line marks the default threshold ($\tau_{KL} = 0.05$).

Table C5

Mean Performance Across Agents (Averaged Over Seeds and Latin Hypercube Samples)

Agent	Fitness	Relative advantage	CSI	KL spikes
A	745.57	117.71	0.87	757.96
B	699.83	163.45	0.85	756.69
C	826.51	36.77	0.98	703.49
D	870.24	-6.96	0.90	736.83

Note. Values are means across seeds and Latin Hypercube samples. Metrics include fitness payoff, relative advantage, coherence stability index (CSI), and KL spike count.

Figure C6

Seed-Wise Robustness of Agent Performance at $\beta = 2.0$ and $h = 0.10$

Note. Boxplots show payoff differences (Agent D minus comparator agent) across 50 seeds. Comparisons are D–A, D–B, and D–C. White markers denote means; box edges represent interquartile ranges; whiskers indicate the full seed distribution with outliers plotted individually.

Table C6

Edge-Case Summary Across Agents (Means Over 50 Seeds)

	Case	Agent A	Agent B	Agent C	Agent D
Volatility	No volatility	F=826.03, CSI=0.94, KL=670.9, RelAdv= =112.41	F=799.75, CSI=0.94, KL=652.58, RelAdv=138.7	F=965.3, CSI=1.12, KL=546.48, RelAdv= -26.86	F=958.59, CSI=1.54, KL=463.68, RelAdv= -20.14
	Extreme volatility	F=867.21, CSI=0.91, KL=715.66, RelAdv=134.0	F=814.25, CSI=0.89, KL=714.98, RelAdv=186.9 6	F=914.73, CSI=0.93, KL=682.6, RelAdv=86.48	F=947.68, CSI=0.91, KL=701.22, RelAdv=53.52
Entropy Cost	No entropy cost ($\delta=0$)	F=845.36, CSI=1.30, KL=670.76, RelAdv=131.2 4	F=810.8, CSI=1.33, KL=658.86, RelAdv=165.8	F=968.15, CSI=1.99, KL=568.98, RelAdv=8.45	F=945.09, CSI=2.07, KL=591.68, RelAdv=31.51
	High entropy cost ($\delta=1$)	F=845.36, CSI=1.30, KL=670.76, RelAdv=131.2 4	F=810.8, CSI=1.33, KL=658.86, RelAdv=165.8	F=968.15, CSI=1.99, KL=568.98, RelAdv=8.45	F=937.53, CSI=2.15, KL=586.18, RelAdv=39.07
Utility structure	Symmetric utilities	F=845.36, CSI=1.30, KL=670.76, RelAdv=131.2 4	F=810.8, CSI=1.33, KL=658.86, RelAdv=165.8	F=968.15, CSI=1.99, KL=568.98, RelAdv=8.45	F=945.32, CSI=2.08, KL=591.18, RelAdv=31.28
Separability	Low discriminability (Δ)	F=417.5, CSI=0.76, KL=651.96, RelAdv=454.7 4	F=449.28, CSI=0.85, KL=646.86, RelAdv=422.9 6	F=816.3, CSI=3.18, KL=536.96, RelAdv=55.94	F=683.73, CSI=1.39, KL=602.94, RelAdv=188.51
	Near-perfect separable	F=1107.4, CSI=3.00, KL=189.34, RelAdv= -0.38	F=1040.8, CSI=2.92, KL=189.32, RelAdv=66.25	F=1107.3, CSI=3.01, KL=189.24, RelAdv= -0.31	F=1107.3, CSI=3.01, KL=189.18, RelAdv= -0.24

Note. Metrics reported are fitness payoff (F), relative advantage (RelAdv), coherence stability index (CSI), and KL spike count (KL). Values are means across 50 seeds for Agents A-D.

Figure C7

Edge-Case Stress Tests for Agent D (Means \pm 95% CI Across 50 Seeds)

Note. Plots show mean values with 95% confidence intervals for fitness, relative advantage, coherence stability index (CSI), and KL spike count. Edge cases include volatility ($h = 0, 1/80, 0.4$), entropy cost ($\delta = 0, 0.10, 1$), and separability (low Δ , baseline, near-perfect).

Figure C8*Edge-Case Heatmaps for Agent D: Volatility (h)*

Note. Seed-wise performance (50 seeds) is shown for volatility levels $h = 0, 1/80, \text{ and } 0.4$.

Heatmaps depict fitness, relative advantage, coherence stability index (CSI), and KL spike count.

Figure C9*Edge-Case Heatmaps for Agent D: Entropy Cost (δ)*

Note. Seed-wise performance (50 seeds) is shown for entropy cost values $\delta = 0, 0.10$, and 1.

Heatmaps depict fitness, relative advantage, coherence stability index (CSI), and KL spike count.

Figure C10*Edge-Case Heatmaps for Agent D: Separability (Δ)*

Note. Seed-wise performance (50 seeds) is shown for separability conditions (low Δ , baseline, near-perfect). Heatmaps depict fitness, relative advantage, coherence stability index (CSI), and KL spike count.

Table C7*Agent D Ablation Results Across Fitness, Relative Advantage, CSI, and KL Spikes*

Condition	Fitness	Relative Adv.	CSI (mean)	KL spikes (count)
Intact	945.7 ± 60.4	30.8 ± 6.4	2.08 ± 0.15	597.4 ± 7.1
Gain-off	712.3 ± 43.1	266.4 ± 28.1	1.33 ± 0.05	658.9 ± 5.6
Update-off	876.9 ± 57.2	91.6 ± 9.4	2.38 ± 0.19	570.8 ± 8.3

Note. Means ± 95% CIs across 50 seeds for *Intact* (full architecture), *Gain-off* (No TBI gain)
Updates-Off (prior frozen)